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MASTERS DISSERTATION

**Where Fires Burn: Modelling Wildfire
Intensity in Space with `inlabru`**

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*A dissertation submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
for the Master of Science in Statistical Ecology*

in the

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School of Mathematics and Statistics

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Gordon Hannah, declare that this dissertation titled, "Where Fires Burn: Modelling Wildfire Intensity in Space with inlabru" and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- this work was carried out while I was a candidate for the degree of Master of Science at the University of St Andrews;
- where any part of this dissertation has previously been submitted for a degree or other qualification at this or any other institution, this has been clearly stated;
- where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed;
- where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this dissertation is entirely my own work;
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help;
- where the dissertation is based on work done jointly with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I contributed myself.

17/08/2025

Gordon A. Hannah 17/08/2025

“Fire is an agent of change in the ecological world, without which life can stagnate. But is the rate of this change now outpacing our ability to cope?”

— Anonymous

UNIVERSITY OF ST ANDREWS

Abstract

Faculty of Science

School of Mathematics and Statistics

Master of Science

Where Fires Burn: Modelling Wildfire Intensity in Space with `inlabru`

by Gordon Hannah

I modelled spatial variation in satellite-detected wildfire occurrence across Great Britain (England, Scotland, and Wales) during April–September 2024 using a log–Gaussian Cox process fitted with the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation as implemented in the `inlabru` package. The modelling dataset comprised $n = 67$ active-fire detections from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer reported by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration Fire Information for Resource Management System, after applying a confidence threshold greater than 65%. Land-cover information was sourced from the United Kingdom Centre for Ecology & Hydrology Land Cover Map 2023 (dominant aggregated class at 1 km resolution). I fitted three specifications: (i) a spatially structured latent field only, (ii) land-cover fixed effects only, and (iii) a combined model. Predictions are presented as *relative* intensity surfaces given known under-detection of small, short-lived fires in temperate Great Britain. The spatial-field model recovered coherent hotspots in southern and eastern England, with lower values in Scotland and Wales, indicating that latent structure can be identified despite sparse data. The land-cover-only model showed near-zero class contrasts when mapped without the spatial field, which I interpret as a consequence of coarse categorical representation and habitat-varying detectability rather than an absence of ecological effects. The combined model reproduced broad spatial contrasts but inflated linear-scale intensity when class effects and the latent field were combined; accordingly, I emphasised relative patterns and summarised predictive uncertainty on the log scale via the posterior standard deviation of $\log \lambda(s)$, which behaves more stably than linear-scale summaries under exponentiation. Overall, this analysis provides Great Britain-wide maps of *relative fire-detection intensity* from limited detections while emphasising the need to calibrate absolute scale. Priority extensions include proportional land-cover compositions and human-activity proxies, confidence-weighted or threshold-sensitivity analyses, offshore buffers or barrier variants of the stochastic partial differential equation approach to temper boundary behaviour, and multi-season spatio-temporal models. These developments would support screening-level, decision-support maps of relative occurrence for prevention, preparedness, and land management planning, without claiming calibrated probabilities or absolute event rates.

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List of Abbreviations

BAP	Biodiversity Action Plan
CI	Credible interval
CV	Coefficient of variation
DIC	Deviance Information Criterion
EPSG	EPSG code for coordinate reference systems
FIRMS	Fire Information for Resource Management System
GB	Great Britain
GMRF	Gaussian Markov Random Field
GRF	Gaussian Random Field
GVA	Gross Value Added
INLA	Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation
IQR	Interquartile range
LCM2023	UKCEH Land Cover Map 2023
LGCP	Log-Gaussian Cox Process
LULC	Land Use/Land Cover
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NI	Northern Ireland
ONS	Office for National Statistics
PC prior	Penalised Complexity prior
P_x	x th percentile (e.g., P90)
SPDE	Stochastic Partial Differential Equation
UK	United Kingdom
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
WAIC	Watanabe–Akaike Information Criterion
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984

List of Symbols

$\lambda(s)$	Spatial intensity function at location s	—
$f(s)$	Latent spatial field at location s	—
β_0	Intercept term in the linear predictor	—
β_j	Coefficient for covariate j	—
$\mathbb{1}_{\{LC=j\}}$	Indicator function for land cover class j	—
σ^2	Marginal variance of the spatial field	—
ρ	Spatial range parameter	m
ν	Smoothness parameter of the Matérn covariance	—
$\varphi_k(s)$	Piecewise linear basis function at mesh vertex k	—
w_k	Gaussian-distributed weight at mesh vertex k	—
s_i, s_j	Spatial locations i and j in the study region	—
λ	Fire intensity	fires km ⁻²
$\log \lambda(s)$	Log-intensity at location s	—
$\text{sd}(\lambda)$	Posterior standard deviation of intensity	—
$\text{mean}(\lambda)$	Posterior mean of intensity	—
$\text{CV}(\lambda)$	Coefficient of variation = $\text{sd}(\lambda)/\text{mean}(\lambda)$	—
$\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$	Posterior s.d. of log-intensity	—
$\Gamma(\nu)$	Gamma function (Matérn covariance)	—
$K_\nu(\cdot)$	Modified Bessel function of the second kind (Matérn)	—
$\ s_i - s_j\ $	Euclidean distance between s_i and s_j	km
$\beta_{LC}(s)$	Fixed effect for land-cover class at s (Models 2–3)	—
σ	Marginal standard deviation of the spatial field	—

This dissertation is dedicated to my brother Stu, taken from us too early. Before you died, I was drifting—chasing the next thing, doing whatever I felt like, living fast and free and never looking too far ahead. Then you were gone.

There was no dramatic moment, no thunderclap—just a quiet shift. A few degrees I didn't even notice at the time.

Wherever I was heading back then, it wasn't here. But now I'm here... and somehow, this is where it's led.

I miss you most when I achieve something. Especially now. I can still hear you—laughing, rolling your eyes, and you'd definitely be saying "Oh right, a master's now? Don't go thinking you're better than the rest of us."

And then—later, quietly: "Show them."

I'm trying, bro. I really am.

There's always a bottle of your favourite beer in the fridge. It takes up space and annoys me—but it's not going anywhere.

This is for you. Always...

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context

Wildfires are an increasing global concern, now occurring in nearly all ecosystems (Archibald et al., 2013). The frequency of large wildfires has risen worldwide in recent decades (Nagy et al., 2018; Drobyshev et al., 2012; Pausas and Fernández-Muñoz, 2012). Human-caused wildfires are also on the rise—in 2024, the United States recorded 7,000 more human-caused fires than in the previous year (National Interagency Fire Center, 2025).

While climate change has been identified as the dominant driver of fire activity in some regions, such as Spain (Rodrigues et al., 2018), other research highlights the combined influence of climate change and population growth (Baltar, Keeley, and Schoenberg, 2014). The impact of climate change on forested areas is particularly acute with respect to fire risk (Schumacher and Bugmann, 2006), while changes in land use and land cover (LULC) are increasingly recognised as key contributors to wildfire occurrence (Parente et al., 2023).

The ecological consequences of greater fire frequency and severity can be substantial. Elevated levels of ash in aquatic environments, for example, can disrupt the gut microbiota of amphibians (Tong et al., 2025), and repeated high-severity fires can shift forest species composition (Trotta et al., 2024). In the longer term, altered fire regimes may lead to widespread transitions towards plant communities better adapted to frequent or intense fires (Steel et al., 2021).

Economic costs are also considerable. In Portugal, burning one-third of a region's area was associated with a short-term economic loss of 1.4% (Sousa, 2021). In southern Europe, even an average fire season can result in losses of €13–21 billion (Meier, Elliott, and Strobl, 2023). In California, wildfire smoke alone caused an estimated \$970 million in crop losses for recreational cannabis in 2021 (Dillis et al., 2023).

Given the growing risks and costs associated with wildfires, accurately modelling and predicting their spatial patterns has become a critical area of research. Predictive modelling is used both to understand wildfire drivers and to support prevention and management strategies. Approaches range from empirical models based on historical occurrence to mechanistic models incorporating vegetation, topography and meteorological data (Archibald et al., 2013; Pausas and Fernández-Muñoz, 2012). In recent years, spatial point process models have become increasingly popular for representing fire occurrence, particularly when ignition events are sparse but spatially structured. Log-Gaussian Cox processes (LGCPs) enable explicit modelling of spatial intensity while accounting for latent spatial structure, often using Integrated

Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) for efficient Bayesian inference (Lindgren, Rue, and Lindström, 2011b; Rue, Martino, and Chopin, 2009b; Bachl et al., 2019-06).

1.2 Motivation

While spatial point process models such as log-Gaussian Cox processes (LGCPs) have been applied in diverse ecological contexts, they remain relatively rare in wildfire studies—especially in temperate ecosystems. In Mediterranean and tropical landscapes, such models are increasingly well developed (Parente et al., 2023), yet the UK remains underrepresented. In particular, spatial statistical models combining LGCPs with environmental covariates such as land cover or elevation have rarely been applied to UK wildfire data. This represents a critical gap, especially as fire risk is expected to rise in the UK under future climate scenarios (Albertson et al., 2010).

Despite the growing global recognition of wildfire risk, research and policy attention in the UK has historically been limited (Albertson et al., 2010). In recent years, however, wildfire incidents have increased across the UK, including in regions not typically associated with high fire risk (Davies and Legg, 2016). Under projected climate scenarios, these trends are expected to accelerate, increasing the urgency of predictive fire modelling.

In Scotland, extensive peatland ecosystems—such as the globally significant Flow Country—are especially vulnerable to wildfire impacts, yet formal monitoring systems remain limited. Peatlands play a crucial role in carbon storage and biodiversity, but once drained or degraded, they become more fire-prone and can burn deeply, releasing long-stored carbon over months or years (Peatland Action, 2023; Arctic Council, 2024). The 2019 Flow Country wildfire, which affected over 60 km², mostly resulted in superficial burning, but impacts were far more severe in degraded areas (Andersen et al., 2024). Restoration efforts that raise water tables have been shown to enhance resilience, highlighting the need for forestry and conservation sectors to adopt targeted strategies that mitigate escalating fire risk.

Forestry is also a major economic sector in Scotland. As of 2015, forestry and timber contributed nearly £285 million in gross value added (GVA), while the broader National Forest Estate supported over 25,000 jobs (Forestry and Land Scotland, 2015). By 2024, the forestry and land sector contributed £1.1 billion to the Scottish economy and employed over 34,000 people (Robertson, 2024). Across the UK, primary wood processing added £2.09 billion GVA and forestry a further £0.76 billion in 2021 (Forest Research, 2023).

Given the likelihood of increasing wildfire frequency and severity, current UK prediction methods may no longer be sufficient (see also the Scottish Wildfire Forum’s fire danger assessment process, as described by Ltd, 2025; *Scottish Wildfire Forum* n.d.). Without accurate forecasts, it becomes more difficult to plan effective fire and fuel breaks or to allocate firefighting resources efficiently. Throughout Europe, models are widely used to predict wildfire occurrence and intensity, but these may not be transferable to the UK, where ignition sources differ. In much of Europe, lightning strikes are a major trigger (San-Miguel-Ayanz, Moreno, and Camia, 2013), whereas in the UK, ignitions are far more often caused by human activity. Additionally, variation in fuel availability, land cover, and land use is likely to influence whether ignitions develop into wildfires (Parente et al., 2023).

This research addresses these challenges by exploring the likelihood of wildfires in the UK using a stochastic partial differential equation (SPDE) approach, with land cover included as a covariate alongside a latent spatial field. The aim is to establish a basis for predicting the conditions under which wildfires are likely to occur. Such a model could support fuel and firebreak planning, guide the targeted deployment of firefighting resources, and inform social mitigation measures—such as regulating muirburns or increasing ranger patrols during high-risk periods.

England presents a distinct challenge in this context. It contains the UK's largest and most densely populated urban areas, and rural–urban interfaces are known hotspots for wildfire ignition. Fires in these areas may pose the greatest threats to human life and infrastructure. During periods of extreme drought, grassland fires also become significantly more likely. Combined with climate projections and extensive moorland coverage in areas such as the Yorkshire Dales, this reinforces the need for improved fire risk modelling in England.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to apply LGCPs to Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) fire detections in the UK using categorical land cover as a covariate. The project contributes both methodologically and practically—by improving understanding of UK-specific wildfire drivers and enhancing tools for future fire risk assessment.

1.3 Statistical Framework and Model Selection

Addressing the research questions outlined above requires a modelling framework capable of handling sparse yet spatially structured data, while accommodating environmental covariates and quantifying uncertainty. Two broad paradigms of statistical inference are available: frequentist and Bayesian.

In frequentist statistics, parameters are treated as fixed but unknown constants, and the goal is to estimate their “true” values from observed data. In Bayesian statistics, parameters are treated as random variables with probability distributions. Rather than returning a single point estimate, Bayesian methods produce a *posterior distribution* that reflects both the observed data and any prior information (via Bayes' theorem). This approach is well suited to ecological applications, where quantifying uncertainty is as important as reporting central tendency, and where posterior predictive distributions are directly interpretable for management decisions.

Bayesian computation can, however, be demanding. Markov chain Monte Carlo methods, once the default for approximating posteriors, are flexible but can be slow for complex models or large datasets. The Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) provides a fast, deterministic alternative for latent Gaussian models, delivering accurate posterior marginals at a fraction of the computational cost.

For spatial ecological problems, including wildfire occurrence, classical frequentist methods often struggle in the presence of spatial autocorrelation, which violates independence assumptions. Approaches such as autocovariate regression, spatial eigenvector mapping, generalised least squares, and spatial autoregressive and conditional autoregressive models can account for spatial structure but typically adjust for its effects rather than modelling the underlying spatial process directly. In contrast, the SPDE approach within INLA (accessed via the `inlabru` package) treats

spatial autocorrelation as a latent Gaussian field to be estimated, enabling prediction across continuous space and providing spatial intensity surfaces that can be interpreted and mapped.

The `inlabru` package integrates cleanly with modern spatial data tools such as `sf` and `terra`, supports flexible model structures, and allows environmental covariates—such as land cover—to be incorporated directly. It also includes built-in functionality for generating predictions and uncertainty summaries over user-defined grids.

Given these advantages, `inlabru` was selected for this study to model GB wildfire occurrence. Its ability to represent latent spatial processes, incorporate covariates, and produce spatial intensity predictions efficiently makes it a practical choice for a predictive framework tailored to GB conditions.

INLA and `inlabru` are increasingly used in ecological and environmental applications, including species distribution, movement and habitat-use modelling, as well as in fields such as disease mapping and biomedical risk modelling where spatial patterns and uncertainty quantification are central.

1.4 Goals and Objectives

Given these considerations, this project applies a log-Gaussian Cox process (LGCP) framework to model the spatial intensity of wildfire detections across GB. I use satellite fire detection data from MODIS via NASA’s Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS), together with relevant environmental predictors such as land cover, to investigate spatial drivers of fire occurrence. The main goals are:

- To model the latent spatial field of GB wildfire detections using a baseline LGCP fitted with INLA and `inlabru`;
- To extend the model by incorporating categorical land cover as a covariate;
- To evaluate model performance and interpret both spatial and covariate effects in the context of fire risk management;
- To demonstrate the broader potential of spatial point process methods for wildfire research in temperate ecosystems.

1.5 Structure of the Dissertation

Following this introduction:

- Chapter 2 describes the datasets, including MODIS/FIRMS fire detections (GB only) and the UKCEH LCM2023 land-cover layers, and explains geographic scope and confidence filtering;
- Chapter 3 details the modelling approach: a baseline LGCP with a latent spatial field, a land cover-only formulation, and a combined model; mesh construction, priors, and SPDE-INLA implementation with `inlabru`; and the prediction/uncertainty workflow;
- Chapter 4 presents model fits and comparisons, including spatial intensity surfaces, land-cover effects, and uncertainty summaries (e.g., $sd(\log \lambda)$, $CV(\lambda)$, and 95% credible-interval widths);

- Chapter 5 discusses findings in context, outlines limitations, and identifies avenues for future research and application;
- Appendices provide supporting material: Appendix A shows raw model outputs; Appendix B contains the full R code used for fitting and prediction and Appendix C contains a R Markdown script to aid in understanding of code creation.

Chapter 2

Data

2.1 Fire Detection Data

Active fire detections were obtained from NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) (NASA Earthdata, 2024), which provides near real-time and archived satellite-based fire products via the Earthdata platform. I used active fire detections from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), whose active-fire product has a nominal spatial resolution of approximately 1 km at nadir on the Terra and Aqua satellites. The MODIS fire algorithm detects thermal anomalies that may be associated with wildfires, agricultural burning, or other high-temperature events.

The data were downloaded in CSV format from the FIRMS global archive and filtered to include only terrestrial locations within Great Britain (GB). These detections span the period **1 April 2024 to 30 September 2024**, yielding a total of **250** records. Coordinates were transformed from geographic (WGS84) to the British National Grid (EPSG:27700) for spatial consistency with the land cover raster and SPDE mesh. Detections in Northern Ireland could not be retained, as the corresponding LCM2023 raster coverage and class values were not fully compatible with the GB products used here; this exclusion is explained in Section 2.2.

To minimise false positives, all records with a confidence score of 0 were removed, excluding 14 detections and leaving **236** points. For modelling, I then applied a stricter filter of confidence $> 65\%$, yielding **67** points (GB only). All model fits, figures, and tables that refer to "observed fires" use this $n = 67$ subset; exploratory summaries that show wider patterns use $n = 236$, unless stated otherwise.

FIRMS fire detections represent individual satellite observations, with each row in the dataset corresponding to a single hotspot detection (not a unique fire event). Table 2.1 summarises key fields used in this study, with definitions based on NASA's official Active Fire Data Attributes (NASA FIRMS, 2024).

TABLE 2.1: Key variables from the NASA FIRMS MODIS Active Fire dataset used in this work.

Variable	Type / Units	Description
latitude, longitude	float (degrees)	Geographic coordinates of the fire-pixel centroid. MODIS active-fire detections have ~ 1 km nominal resolution.
acq_date	string (YYYY-MM-DD)	Acquisition date in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC).
acq_time	integer (HHMM)	Acquisition time in UTC (24-hour clock, no colon).
satellite	string	Satellite platform (Terra or Aqua).
instrument	string	Sensor instrument: MODIS.
confidence	integer (0–100)	Algorithm confidence that a thermal anomaly is a true fire; higher values indicate greater certainty.
brightness	float (Kelvin)	Brightness temperature in the mid-infrared channel used for fire detection (MODIS $4 \mu\text{m}$ band).
bright_t31	float (Kelvin)	Brightness temperature in MODIS Band 31 ($11 \mu\text{m}$).
frp	float (MW)	Fire Radiative Power, an energy-based proxy for fire intensity.
daynight	string (D/N)	D if acquired during daylight; N if at night.
version	string	Product version label for MODIS (e.g., 6.1 or 6.1NRT).

2.2 Geographic Scope

Although the original aim was to model the whole United Kingdom (UK), all analyses in this dissertation are restricted to Great Britain (GB; England, Scotland, and Wales). This choice ensures that the modelling domain, the SPDE mesh, and the covariate raster (UKCEH LCM2023, 1 km dominant aggregate classes) are aligned without additional harmonisation steps. The GB and Northern Ireland (NI) LCM2023 products are distributed separately and were not combined here; the modelling boundary follows the Office for National Statistics (ONS) GB national boundary used for mesh construction.

All data filtering, mesh generation, land-cover extraction, and prediction were therefore performed within the GB land mask. Northern Ireland is excluded from all modelling and visualisation.

2.3 Land Cover Data

Land cover information for this study was obtained from the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) Land Cover Map 2023 (LCM2023), specifically the 1 km *dominant aggregated-class* raster product for Great Britain (GB). Each 1 km grid cell is

assigned to one of ten aggregated classes derived from higher-resolution (10 m and 25 m) products, aligned to Biodiversity Action Plan (BAP) Broad Habitats (Table 2.2).

The LCM2023 raster was used in its native British National Grid (EPSG:27700) projection. Only the GB product was used; the separate Northern Ireland product was not combined because all analyses and predictions are restricted to GB (Section 2.2). Land-cover class values were extracted at each fire-detection location and used as a categorical covariate in the LGCP models.

The raster used (`gb20231cm1km_dominant_aggregate.tif`) encodes classes with integer identifiers (1–10), each mapping to one of the ten aggregated categories. Figure 2.1 shows the spatial distribution of aggregated land-cover classes across GB.

The dataset is cited as (Marston et al., 2024). Use of the data was licensed under the Environment Digimap Educational User Licence for academic research purposes only.

TABLE 2.2: UKCEH LCM2023 aggregated classes and their corresponding UKCEH Land Cover Classes and BAP Broad Habitats.

Agg. ID	Aggregate Class	LC ID	UKCEH Land Cover Class	BAP Broad Habitat
1	Broadleaved woodland	1	Deciduous woodland	Broadleaved, mixed and yew woodland
2	Coniferous woodland	2	Coniferous woodland	Coniferous woodland
3	Arable	3	Arable	Arable and horticulture
4	Improved grassland	4	Improved grassland	Improved grassland
5	Semi-natural grassland	5	Neutral grassland	Neutral grassland
		6	Calcareous grassland	Calcareous grassland
		7	Acid grassland	Acid grassland
		8	Fen	Fen, marsh and swamp
6	Mountain, heath and bog	9	Heather	Dwarf shrub heath
		10	Heather grassland	Dwarf shrub heath
		11	Bog	Bog
		12	Inland rock	Inland rock
7	Saltwater	13	Saltwater	(No BAP equivalent)
8	Freshwater	14	Freshwater	Standing water and canals; rivers and streams
9	Coastal	15	Supralittoral rock	Supralittoral rock
		16	Supralittoral sediment	Supralittoral sediment
		17	Littoral rock	Littoral rock
		18	Littoral sediment	Littoral sediment
		19	Saltmarsh	Saltmarsh
10	Built-up areas and gardens	20	Urban	Built-up areas and gardens
		21	Suburban	Built-up areas and gardens

FIGURE 2.1: Dominant aggregated land cover classes across GB in 2023 (UKCEH LCM2023). Each 1 km² grid cell is coloured by the most prevalent aggregated class (Table 2.2). These classes were extracted at fire-detection locations and used as a categorical covariate in the LGCP models. Most fires occurred in Arable (47.8%, 32/67) and Built-up areas and gardens (31.3%, 21/67), with smaller shares in Improved grassland (9.0%, 6/67), Mountain, heath and bog (7.5%, 5/67), Semi-natural grassland (3.0%, 2/67), and Coniferous woodland (1.5%, 1/67); other classes recorded 0% in the modelling subset (confidence > 65%, $n = 67$).

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Software and Packages

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.4.0 (R Core Team, 2024). Spatial modelling used INLA (Rue, Martino, and Chopin, 2009a) and `inlabru` (Thompson et al., 2023). Spatial data processing and visualisation used `sf` (Pebesma, 2023) and, where required for legacy workflows, `sp` (Bivand, Pebesma, and Gómez-Rubio, 2013) for vector data; `terra` (Hijmans, 2024) and `raster` (Hijmans, 2023) were used for raster data. Figures were created with `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016), and tabular manipulation with `dplyr` (Wickham et al., 2023).

The national boundary for Great Britain, used for mesh construction and figure basemaps, was obtained from the UK ONS Open Geography Portal (Office for National Statistics, 2024).

All data processing and modelling workflows were scripted in R to ensure reproducibility; the complete code is provided in Appendix B.

3.2 Spatial Point Pattern and Covariates

A spatial point process is a stochastic process that generates a finite or countably infinite set of points within a region, describing how random events—such as fire ignitions—are located in space. This framework underpins the LGCP models used here, where active fire detections are treated as point events.

The point pattern comprised 236 active fire detections in GB recorded by MODIS between 1 April and 30 September 2024 (Section 2.1). Conditional on a latent Gaussian field, these points are modelled as an inhomogeneous Poisson process. Each detection is associated with planar coordinates and a categorical land-cover class extracted from the 1 km aggregated UKCEH LCM2023 raster (Section 2.3). To limit false positives, I used a strict confidence threshold for modelling: only records with confidence $> 65\%$ were retained, yielding $n = 67$ fire points (GB only).¹

Land cover was encoded as a factor with ten aggregated habitat classes (Table 2.2). Coordinates were projected to British National Grid (EPSG:27700) for consistency with the land-cover raster and the SPDE mesh.

¹Exploratory summaries elsewhere use $n = 236$ after removing zero-confidence detections; all model fits and figures that refer to “observed fires” use the $n = 67$ subset.

3.3 Mesh Construction and Spatial Discretisation

To model spatial variation in fire intensity, I used the stochastic partial differential equation (SPDE) approach of Lindgren, Rue, and Lindström (2011a), which links a continuous Gaussian random field (GRF) to a discretised Gaussian Markov random field (GMRF) via a finite-element representation on a triangulated mesh. This enables efficient Bayesian inference with integrated nested Laplace approximation (INLA; Rue, Martino, and Chopin (2009a)).

The spatial domain (GB) was discretised using a constrained Delaunay triangulation, which yields well-shaped elements and avoids long, thin triangles that can reduce numerical stability. The Delaunay property ensures that no mesh vertex lies inside the circumcircle of any triangle; the corresponding Voronoi diagram has vertices at the triangle circumcentres. To mitigate boundary artefacts, the mesh was extended beyond the coastline with a coarser outer buffer.

The mesh was constructed with `inla.mesh.2d`, using the ONS national boundary as the internal constraint. Parameters were `cutoff = 10 km` (to prevent over-refinement in clustered areas), `maximum internal edge = 20 km`, and `maximum outer edge = 80 km`. The resulting mesh contained 2,391 vertices, balancing resolution to capture spatial variation with computational cost (Figure 3.1).

The latent spatial field $f(s)$ was represented as a zero-mean Matérn GRF on the mesh via piecewise linear basis functions:

$$f(s) = \sum_{k=1}^n \phi_k(s) w_k,$$

where $\phi_k(s)$ are vertex-associated basis functions and w_k are Gaussian weights. The Matérn covariance,

$$\text{Cov}(f(s_i), f(s_j)) = \sigma^2 \frac{2^{1-\nu}}{\Gamma(\nu)} \left(\frac{\|s_i - s_j\|}{\rho} \right)^\nu K_\nu \left(\frac{\|s_i - s_j\|}{\rho} \right),$$

is governed by the marginal variance σ^2 , the (practical) range ρ , and the smoothness ν (fixed under the SPDE formulation).

I used penalised-complexity (PC) priors (Fuglstad et al., 2019; Simpson et al., 2017) for the Matérn parameters as implemented in INLA:

$$\Pr(\sigma > 1) = 0.01, \quad \Pr(\rho < 50 \text{ km}) = 0.5,$$

corresponding to a weakly informative prior that favours smaller marginal variance and sets a median practical range of 50 km. These are consistent with the SPDE specification used in the fitted models.

FIGURE 3.1: SPDE mesh for Great Britain constructed via constrained Delaunay triangulation. Internal refinement reflects the distribution of observed fire detections (red points; $n = 67$, confidence $> 65\%$), while a coarser outer buffer reduces boundary artefacts and computation.

3.4 Model Formulation and Fitting

To disentangle large-scale land cover effects from residual spatial structure in wild-fire occurrence, I fitted three log-Gaussian Cox process (LGCP) models. In all cases, fire detections are assumed to arise from a Poisson point process with spatially varying intensity $\lambda(s)$, and the latent field is estimated via the SPDE-INLA framework (Sections 3.2–3.3). In `inlabru`, a global intercept is included by default in the linear predictor unless it is explicitly removed with `-1/+0` or replaced by a user-supplied `Intercept(1)` component. Where the schematic code in Section 3.4 writes `Intercept(1)`, the Appendix B implementation relies on the default intercept; these are equivalent for our models.

- **Model 1 (spatial field only)** tests for residual spatial structure without land cover covariates.
- **Model 2 (land cover only)** isolates systematic differences between land cover classes, omitting the spatial field from prediction.
- **Model 3 (combined)** estimates land cover effects while also accounting for residual spatial structure.

Model 1: spatial field only.

$$\log \lambda(s) = \beta_0 + f(s),$$

where β_0 is an intercept and $f(s)$ is a zero-mean latent Gaussian field represented with the SPDE Matérn approximation. I use PC priors consistent with the fitted code: $\Pr(\sigma > 1) = 0.01$ for the field standard deviation and $\Pr(\rho < 50 \text{ km}) = 0.5$ for the range. In `inlabru`:

```
components = coordinates ~
  Intercept(1) + field(coordinates, model = spde)
```

Model 2: land cover only.

$$\log \lambda(s) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j \neq \text{Arable}} \beta_j \mathbb{1}_{\{\text{LC}=j\}},$$

treating land cover (LC) as a factor with “Arable” as the reference. We place a PC prior on the factor’s standard deviation via `pc.prec` such that $\Pr(\text{sd} > 0.5) = 0.01$. To stabilise estimates I fit with the same SPDE structure as Model 1, but for the *maps* labelled “land cover only” I set $f(s) \equiv 0$ at prediction time to show the fixed-effect contribution in isolation. In `inlabru`:

```
components = coordinates ~
  Intercept(1) +
  landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
    hyper = list(prec = list(
      prior = "pc.prec", param = c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
  field(coordinates, model = spde)
```

Model 3: combined model.

$$\log \lambda(s) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j \neq \text{Arable}} \beta_j \mathbb{1}_{\{\text{LC}=j\}} + f(s),$$

combining land cover fixed effects with the latent spatial field $f(s)$. Priors for $f(s)$ match Model 1. In `inlabru`:

```
components = coordinates ~
  Intercept(1) +
  landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
    hyper = list(prec = list(
      prior = "pc.prec", param = c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
  field(coordinates, model = spde)
```

All models were fitted using `lgcp()` in `inlabru`, with the domain supplied by the triangulated SPDE mesh (Section 3.3). Predictions were generated on a regular grid and combined with LCM2023 land cover values (Section 2.3). I report $\lambda(s)$ as *intensity per km²*; since the fitted intensity is per m², maps on the intensity scale multiply $\lambda(s)$ by 10^6 to convert to km² units (I do not divide by grid-cell area when plotting intensities). Absolute totals per cell, if needed, are approximated by $\lambda(s) \times \text{area}(\text{cell})$.

3.5 Prediction and Inference

For each fitted LGCP model, predictions of fire detection intensity $\lambda(s)$ were generated across the GB study area using a regular integration grid aligned to the spatial mesh. Posterior summaries of the latent spatial field and land cover effects were extracted with built-in `inlabru` functions. Predicted log-intensities were exponentiated and rescaled to represent the expected number of detections per km^2 , based on the resolution of the clipped output raster.

To compare models and interpret behaviour, I used:

- **Posterior intensity maps** (spatial field-only, land-cover-only, and full), to visualise broad spatial contrasts in predicted occurrence intensity;
- **Uncertainty diagnostics**, including $\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$, coefficient of variation $\text{CV}(\lambda)$, and 95% credible-interval width for λ , alongside posterior summaries of SPDE hyperparameters.

Numerical and spatial comparison outputs are presented in Chapter 4, with interpretation in the context of GB fire occurrence and model behaviour.

Display scale. When we show component-only predictions (e.g., $\sim \exp(\text{field})$), the maps are on a **relative** scale to emphasise spatial contrasts; the global intercept is part of the fitted linear predictor by default and affects the overall level but not the spatial pattern.

3.6 Model Cross-Validation

I do not report the Watanabe–Akaike Information Criterion (WAIC) or the deviance information criterion (DIC) for our LGCP models. Both criteria are based on point-wise log-predictive densities and a factorization into conditionally independent observational units. In LGCPs fitted by numerical quadrature, the dataset is augmented with a large number of integration (pseudo-zero) points; computing WAIC/DIC on this augmented set is dominated by pseudo-observations and is therefore not interpretable. Even when restricted to observed events, high-dimensional latent Gaussian spatial fields induce strong dependence, yielding unstable effective parameter counts for DIC and unreliable WAIC behavior in such non-regular hierarchical settings. (Spiegelhalter et al., 2002; Vehtari, Gelman, and Gabry, 2017; Baddeley, Rubak, and Turner, 2015; Rue, Martino, and Chopin, 2009a)

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Exploratory Analysis

4.1.1 Spatial Distribution

FIGURE 4.1: Spatial distribution of FIRMS fire detections across GB (Apr–Sep 2024). Each red point represents an individual MODIS detection. Concentrations are greatest in the south and east of England, with comparatively few detections in Scotland or Wales.

Fire detections were not evenly distributed across GB. As shown in Figure 4.1, most detections occurred in the south and east of England, with fewer in Scotland and

Wales. Table 4.1 summarises detections by GB region, reporting counts and descriptive statistics for brightness, confidence, and brightness temperature. Unless stated otherwise, all summaries in this subsection use the exploratory dataset after removing zero-confidence detections (GB only; $n = 236$).

Region	Fires	Brightness						Confidence (%)						Temperature (K)					
		Min	25%	Median	Mean	75%	Max	Min	25%	Median	Mean	75%	Max	Min	25%	Median	Mean	75%	Max
East Midlands	26	300.8	303.1	305.7	306.8	307.8	327.4	24	45	53	54	65	85	281.9	286.3	288.9	288.1	290.1	295.2
East of England	47	303.0	308.3	311.8	317.1	319.0	369.0	10	52	63	61	70	100	276.5	293.8	296.2	295.1	298.2	302.0
London	1	305.8	305.8	305.8	305.8	305.8	305.8	49	49	49	49	49	49	294.8	294.8	294.8	294.8	294.8	294.8
North West	2	300.2	302.1	304.0	304.0	305.9	307.8	21	29	37	37	44	52	280.4	284.6	288.7	288.7	292.9	297.0
Scotland	14	301.9	302.9	307.1	309.7	311.5	328.1	16	41	58	55	69	82	279.3	283.3	287.9	287.6	291.2	297.3
South East	31	302.2	308.0	313.1	313.7	319.1	333.1	39	57	63	64	72	88	285.6	291.6	296.0	295.1	298.1	302.5
South West	30	301.6	304.3	307.9	310.5	314.2	331.5	39	54	62	61	67	85	280.5	287.9	293.7	291.5	294.9	298.2
Wales	11	300.3	302.5	312.4	309.5	316.2	318.5	23	43	48	49	56	70	277.8	286.1	288.5	289.9	296.2	300.7
West Midlands	14	300.9	302.4	306.1	310.1	310.9	343.4	35	48	56	57	63	93	284.1	289.2	290.9	290.4	292.6	296.2
Yorkshire and The Humber	52	300.1	303.5	310.0	309.4	313.8	328.0	12	39	51	52	62	98	275.5	285.0	288.1	289.0	292.7	308.2
NA	2	313.2	316.2	319.1	319.1	322.1	325.0	47	60	74	74	87	100	280.2	284.5	288.8	288.8	293.1	297.4

TABLE 4.1: Summary statistics for FIRMS fire detections in GB (Apr–Sep 2024), grouped by GB region. For each region, the table reports the number of detections and descriptive statistics (minimum, quartiles, mean, maximum) for brightness, confidence (%), and brightness temperature (K). Summaries use the exploratory dataset after removing zero-confidence detections ($n = 236$).

4.1.2 Summary of Fire Counts by Region

Based on the counts in Table 4.1, Yorkshire and the Humber (52 detections) and the East of England (47) together account for **43.0%** of the detections listed (99/230). The four highest-count regions—Yorkshire and the Humber, East of England, South East (31), and South West (30)—contribute **69.6%** of detections (160/230). London recorded a single detection and the North West recorded two; given the predominantly urban character of London, a low number of satellite fire detections is unsurprising.

Wales reported 11 detections and Scotland 14. Despite extensive areas of upland grassland, heath, and peat, their lower counts may reflect fewer ignition sources associated with lower population density and/or variable satellite detection conditions. These descriptive counts are not interpreted as evidence of inherently lower fire susceptibility.

All percentages above are computed from the totals in Table 4.1. The modelling subset uses only detections with confidence $> 65\%$ ($n = 67$) and is used for all models.

4.1.3 Temporal Patterns

FIGURE 4.2: Number of fire detections per month (GB only). A clear seasonal peak is visible in August and September 2024.

Monthly detection counts (Figure 4.2) show a clear late-summer peak in August–September 2024. Counts reflect the exploratory dataset after removing zero-confidence detections (confidence > 0 ; $n = 236$). This pattern is consistent with typical seasonal fire *activity* profiles in temperate regions; we do not model or attribute meteorological drivers here.

4.1.4 Detection Characteristics

Unless stated otherwise, summaries in this subsection use the exploratory GB dataset after removing zero-confidence detections (confidence > 0 ; $n = 236$).

Figure 4.3 shows the distribution of detection confidence. Most detections fall in the moderate–high range, with a mode near 60–70% in this dataset.

FIGURE 4.3: Histogram of FIRMS detection confidence (GB; $n = 236$). Vertical dashed lines mark the 1st quartile, median, and 3rd quartile.

Fire *brightness* values (MODIS 4 μm channel; units K) were typically concentrated between 300 and 320 (Figure 4.4), with a smaller number of higher-intensity detections above 350.

FIGURE 4.4: Histogram of FIRMS *brightness* (K) for GB detections. Vertical dashed lines mark the 1st quartile, median, and 3rd quartile.

Brightness temperature from MODIS Band 31 (11 μm ; K) followed a roughly symmetric distribution centred around ~ 290 K (Figure 4.5).

FIGURE 4.5: Histogram of brightness temperature (K; MODIS Band 31) for GB detections. Vertical dashed lines mark the 1st quartile, median, and 3rd quartile.

4.2 Results

Posterior predictions (e.g. fitted spatial fields and intensity surfaces) were computed from Monte Carlo samples generated using INLA’s internal C++ random number generator. While reproducibility can be improved by fixing a random seed, the reported predictive means remain sample-based approximations of the posterior expectation and may therefore differ slightly between runs. These differences reflect Monte Carlo variability rather than genuine differences in the underlying posterior distribution.

4.2.1 Predicted Fire Intensity from Spatial Field Model

The spatial field-only LGCP (Model 1; see Section 3.4) estimated spatial variation in fire intensity across GB, producing a posterior mean intensity surface on a regular grid of 22,500 locations. Raw predictions are on the model’s native (unitless) scale and per grid cell (Appendix A.1); values ranged from near zero to $> 2,400$ with a median of 6.88, and were strongly right-skewed.

For interpretability, we express intensity as expected detections per km^2 by rescaling the fitted $\lambda(s)$ (events per m^2) by 10^6 ; no grid-cell area term is applied to intensity maps. Most land pixels had predicted intensities below 4 fires km^{-2} , with localised higher values primarily in southern and eastern England. Because totals on the intensity scale can be inflated by heavy-tailed posterior draws and satellite under-detection, interpretation focuses on relative spatial contrasts rather than absolute counts.

Figure 4.6 shows the posterior mean intensity surface (fires km^{-2}), and Table 4.2 summarises its distribution over land pixels.

FIGURE 4.6: Predicted fire intensity from the spatial field-only LGCP model, expressed as the expected number of fire detections per square kilometre. Warmer colours indicate areas with higher predicted intensity across GB.

TABLE 4.2: Summary statistics for posterior mean fire intensity (fires per km²) across GB, estimated from the spatial field-only LGCP model.

Statistic	Value
Minimum	0.03
First quartile	0.52
Median	1.73
Mean	6.25
Third quartile	10.53
Maximum	46.05
NA	8,331
Total expected fires (sum over land)	21,227

4.2.2 Land Cover Effects

To assess whether land cover was associated with spatial variation in fire occurrence, the land cover-only LGCP (Model 2; see Section 3.4) was fitted with land cover as a categorical covariate.

After accounting for spatial structure during model fitting (via a latent spatial field included for estimation), the estimated log-relative land-cover effects were extremely small (Table 4.3). Posterior means were close to zero and all 95% credible intervals overlap zero, indicating no strong evidence that fire intensity differed systematically between land-cover types once spatial autocorrelation was modelled explicitly.

Figure 4.7 shows the predicted spatial distribution under the land cover-only formulation. These predictions exclude the spatial random field and therefore reflect only the fixed-effect contribution of each land-cover class, expressed relative to Arable land (the reference category).

TABLE 4.3: Estimated land-cover effects from the land cover-only LGCP, expressed as *log-relative intensity* (relative to Arable land).

Land Cover	Mean	Std. Dev.	2.5%	Median	97.5%	Mode
Built-up areas and gardens	0.002	0.008	-0.013	0.002	0.017	0.002
Coniferous woodland	0.000	0.008	-0.015	0.000	0.015	0.000
Improved grassland	0.000	0.008	-0.014	0.000	0.015	0.000
Mountain, heath and bog	0.000	0.008	-0.015	0.000	0.015	0.000
Semi-natural grassland	0.000	0.008	-0.015	0.000	0.015	0.000

4.2.3 Full Model Effects

The combined LGCP (Model 3; see Section 3.4) included both land cover fixed effects and the spatial latent field. Posterior mean predictions were generated across GB, producing estimates on the latent log-intensity scale and, via exponentiation, as expected fire detections per km².

FIGURE 4.7: Predicted *relative intensity* from the land cover-only LGCP, excluding the spatial field. Each location's value reflects the contribution of its land-cover class to expected fire detections, relative to Arable land.

Table 4.4 summarises these predictions. While the median predicted fire intensity was $1.72 \text{ fires km}^{-2}$, a small number of grid cells had extremely large log-intensity values (maximum = 1635.30), which caused exponentiated means and maxima to reach numerical infinity. This strong right-skew motivated the use of a clipped intensity surface for interpretation.

To determine an appropriate clipping threshold, the distribution of log-intensity predictions was inspected (Figure 4.8). Most values lay below $\log(\lambda) = 3$, but a long right tail was evident. The 70th percentile (log-scale threshold ≈ 2.62 , equivalent to $\approx 13.74 \text{ fires km}^{-2}$) was selected as a defensible cut-off, retaining the majority of meaningful spatial variation while removing rare, model-driven spikes unlikely to reflect real fire patterns.

The clipped prediction surface (Figure 4.9) highlights broad spatial patterns in expected fire activity, driven jointly by land cover and residual spatial structure.

TABLE 4.4: Summary statistics for posterior mean predictions from the full LGCP model (Model 3). Log-intensity values are on the latent scale; intensities are exponentiated to give expected fire detections per km^2 .

Scale	Statistic	Value
<i>Log-Intensity</i>	Minimum	-226.86
	First quartile	-0.33
	Median	0.54
	Mean	33.83
	Third quartile	5.79
	Maximum	1635.30
<i>Intensity (fires/km^2)</i>	Minimum	0.00
	First quartile	0.72
	Median	1.72
	Third quartile	327.26
	Maximum	—
	Total fires	—

Note. Maximum and total on the intensity scale overflow to $+\infty$ for rare extreme cells; handled in post-model processing. Values omitted here for clarity.

FIGURE 4.8: Histogram of predicted log-intensity values from the full LGCP model (Model 3), zoomed to range 0–20. Vertical dashed lines mark the 60%, 70%, and 80% quantiles. The 70th percentile (green) was used as the clipping threshold prior to exponentiation, corresponding to ≈ 13.74 fires km^{-2} .

4.2.4 Predicted Fire Intensity from Full LGCP Model

The combined LGCP (Model 3; see Section 3.4) incorporated both a spatial random field and categorical land cover covariates. Posterior mean fire intensity was estimated across GB and expressed as expected fires km^{-2} . To aid interpretation and prevent a small number of extreme predictions from dominating the colour scale, values were clipped at the 70th percentile of the posterior log-intensity distribution (≈ 2.62 on the log scale, equivalent to 13.74 fires km^{-2}) prior to exponentiation. Summary statistics are reported in Table 4.5.

FIGURE 4.9: Posterior mean fire intensity from the full LGCP model (Model 3), clipped at the 70th percentile of the log-intensity distribution (≈ 13.74 fires km^{-2}). Warmer colours indicate higher predicted intensity.

TABLE 4.5: Posterior summary statistics for predicted fire intensity (fires km^{-2}) from the full LGCP model (Model 3), after clipping at the 70th percentile of the log-intensity distribution.

Statistic	Value
Minimum	0.00
First quartile	13.79
Median	13.79
Mean	11.26
Third quartile	13.79
Maximum (clipped)	13.79
Missing (NA)	559,711
Total expected fires (over land)	2,590,262

Across all valid land pixels ($n = 230,039$), the mean predicted intensity was 11.26 fires km^{-2} , giving an estimated total of approximately 2.6 million fires. This is far greater than the 67 observed fire events in the dataset, reflecting both the right-skewed nature of the posterior predictions and potential model overestimation, which is discussed in Chapter 5.

4.3 Uncertainty Representation

In a Bayesian framework, each parameter or prediction is associated with a posterior distribution. A 95% credible interval (CI) is the range $[L, U]$ such that $\Pr(\theta \in [L, U] \mid \text{data}) = 0.95$.

I summarise predictive uncertainty on land pixels in three complementary ways:

1. **95% CI width for intensity** λ (fires km^{-2}): an absolute measure of imprecision.
2. **Coefficient of variation** $\text{CV}(\lambda) = \text{sd}(\lambda) / \text{mean}(\lambda)$: a unitless, relative measure that aids spatial comparison.
3. **sd(log λ)**: for the full model, I also report the posterior standard deviation of the log-intensity, which is stable under exponentiation and informative when the intensity scale is heavy-tailed.

Uncertainty is presented with maps to illustrate spatial patterns and with small tables reporting distributional quantiles; posterior summaries of hyperparameters (e.g., SPDE range and field standard deviation) are also reported.

Reported predictive means and uncertainties are based on posterior samples. For hyperparameters with very large posterior scales (e.g. standard deviations on the order of 10^4 – 10^5), minor differences between runs (on the order of 10^3) reflect Monte Carlo variation rather than substantive changes in inference.

4.3.1 Uncertainty — Model 1 (spatial field only)

Relative uncertainty is high across land pixels (Figure 4.10), with $\text{CV}(\lambda)$ exceeding 1 everywhere. Absolute uncertainty, summarised by the 95% credible-interval width for intensity λ , shows a similar spatial pattern (Figure 4.11), with the widest

intervals concentrated in southern and eastern GB. Exact distributional summaries (quantiles and tail behaviour) are reported in Tables 4.6–4.7. Posterior SPDE hyperparameters (Table 4.8) indicate a broadly correlated but high-variance latent field, which explains the wide intervals on the intensity scale. Accordingly, the Model 1 maps are most reliable for *relative* contrasts (hotspots versus elsewhere) rather than precise pointwise rates.

FIGURE 4.10: Model 1: relative uncertainty map, shown as $CV(\lambda) = \text{sd}(\lambda)/\text{mean}(\lambda)$, over land pixels.

TABLE 4.6: Model 1: relative uncertainty (CV) over land pixels.

Statistic	Value
Min	2.626
Q1	3.411
Median	3.781
Mean	4.337
Q3	4.390
Max	18.698
P90	5.866
P99	13.286
Share CV < 0.5	0.000
Share CV < 1.0	0.000
<i>N</i> (land)	3,399
NAs (land)	0

FIGURE 4.11: Model 1: absolute uncertainty map, shown as 95% CI width for intensity λ (fires km^{-2}), over land pixels.

TABLE 4.7: Model 1: 95% CI width (fires km^{-2}) over land pixels.

Statistic	Value
Min	13.786
Q1	354.915
Median	1,869.368
Mean	7,872.276
Q3	13,065.029
Max	62,062.700
P90	23,595.026
P99	45,680.358

TABLE 4.8: Model 1: SPDE hyperparameters (posterior summaries).

	Mean	SD	2.5%	50%	97.5%
Range for field (m)	325,185.889	81,177.25	197,286.754	314,588.804	514,810.942
Stdev for field	2.214	0.380	1.562	2.181	3.054

4.3.2 Uncertainty — Model 2 (land–cover only)

Predictive uncertainty for the land–cover–only model was uniformly small across GB. The coefficient of variation map (Figure 4.12) shows values that are consistently well below 1 over land pixels, with a very narrow colour-bar range; the corresponding absolute uncertainty (95% credible–interval width) is likewise negligible at the map scale (Figure 4.13). These patterns arise because predictions for this model exclude the spatial random field and depend only on class-level fixed effects, which are estimated with high precision when pooled across pixels of the same class (cf. Section 3.4). Numerical summaries are reported in Tables 4.9 and 4.10, and posterior summaries of the associated hyperparameters are provided for completeness in Table 4.11; note, however, that the spatial field is not used in the Model 2 prediction surface and therefore contributes minimally to its uncertainty.

FIGURE 4.12: Model 2: relative uncertainty, shown as $CV(\lambda) = \text{sd}(\lambda)/\text{mean}(\lambda)$, over land pixels. Note the small colour-bar range (max ≈ 0.009).

TABLE 4.9: Model 2: relative uncertainty (CV) over land pixels.

Statistic	Value
Min	0.000
Q1	0.000
Median	0.008
Mean	0.006
Q3	0.008
Max	0.008
P90	0.008
P99	0.008
Share CV < 0.5	1.000
Share CV < 1.0	1.000
N (land)	3,399
NAs (land)	0

FIGURE 4.13: Model 2: absolute uncertainty, shown as 95% CI width for intensity λ (fires km^{-2}), over land pixels.

TABLE 4.10: Model 2: 95% CI width (fires km^{-2}) over land pixels.

Statistic	Value
Min	0.000
Q1	0.000
Median	0.029
Mean	0.022
Q3	0.030
Max	0.031
P90	0.030
P99	0.031
N (land)	3,399
NAs (land)	0

TABLE 4.11: Model 2: hyperparameters (posterior summaries).

	Mean	SD	2.5%	50%	97.5%
Precision for landcover	17,279.791	18.316	17,239.269	17,281.356	17,310.24
Range for field (m)	1,003,897.009	700.378	1,002,256.932	1,004,920.98	1,004,453.232
Stdev for field	2.554	0.005	2.543	2.555	2.56

4.3.3 Uncertainty — Model 3 (full: land cover + spatial field)

For the combined model, I summarise predictive uncertainty primarily on the log scale using $\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$, which is stable under exponentiation and comparable across space. The corresponding map (Figure 4.14) shows broadly higher uncertainty around predicted hotspots and lower values elsewhere. Its distribution is summarised in Table 4.12. In line with this choice of metric, we interpret uncertainty *comparatively* (i.e., where uncertainty is higher or lower) rather than in absolute intensity units.

For transparency, I also report uncertainty on the intensity scale as the width of the 95% credible interval for λ (fires km^{-2}). Because exponentiating heavy-tailed log-intensity draws produces a few extreme cells that dominate the colour scale, I present a *clipped* map with the colour bar capped at the land-pixel 90th percentile (Figure 4.15); the full, *unclipped* distribution is reported in Table 4.13. These summaries make clear that intensity-scale intervals are strongly right-skewed and should be interpreted with caution. Posterior hyperparameter summaries are reported in Table 4.14.

FIGURE 4.14: Model 3: uncertainty shown as $\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$ over land pixels.

TABLE 4.12: Model 3: $\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$ over land pixels (summary statistics).

Statistic	Value
Min	11.277
Q1	15.008
Median	15.990
Mean	16.062
Q3	17.012
Max	22.351
P90	18.032
P99	19.844
N (land)	3,375

FIGURE 4.15: Model 3: 95% CI width for intensity λ (fires km^{-2}), colour scale clipped at the land-pixel 90th percentile (P90). Unclipped values are reported in Table 4.13.

TABLE 4.13: Model 3: 95% CI width (fires km^{-2}) over land pixels (*unclipped*). Extremely large values arise from exponentiation of heavy-tailed log predictions.

Statistic	Value
Min	0.000000e+00
Q1	1.060071e+15
Median	6.653156e+28
Mean	1.862894e+304
Q3	1.010913e+80
Max	6.071274e+307
P90	3.405441e+154
P99	2.173852e+269
<i>N</i> (land)	3.324000e+03
Non-finite (land)	5.100000e+01

TABLE 4.14: Model 3: hyperparameters (posterior summaries).

	Mean	SD	2.5%	50%	97.5%
Precision for landcover	6,101.122	6.478	6,089.499	6,100.782	6,114.880
Range for field (m)	30,689.215	34.440	30,611.411	30,692.896	30,744.032
Stdev for field	18.029	0.010	18.006	18.030	18.046

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion of Results

As shown in Chapter 4, spatial point process modelling (via an LGCP) can provide detailed, spatially explicit predictions of wildfire occurrence across Great Britain (GB; England, Wales and Scotland). In this study I analysed $n = 67$ FIRMS active-fire detections (after filtering; NI excluded for consistency with the modelling domain). Unlike some European countries with nationally coordinated wildfire structures—such as Portugal, where Agência para a Gestão Integrada de Fogos Rurais provides strategic national coordination of the Integrated Rural Fire Management System, and Italy, where national civil protection and the National Fire Corps coordinate wildfire operations—there is **no single GB-wide agency** dedicated specifically to wildfire response or reporting; responsibility sits primarily with individual fire and rescue services, and recording remains fragmented (Agência para a Gestão Integrada de Fogos Rurais (AGIF), 2025; Dipartimento della Protezione Civile, 2024; National Fire Chiefs Council, 2025).

GB fire and rescue services also face sustained capacity pressures (financial constraints, recruitment and retention challenges, and declining on-call availability), which can affect response (Constabulary and Services, 2024). Moreover, many small vegetation fires go unreported, and even attended incidents have historically been inconsistently recorded, meaning some events may only be reported once they have grown larger and are harder to manage (Forestry Commission, 2014; McMorrow, 2011).

In this context, accurate spatial prediction models can support resource allocation, training, and operational preparedness, and inform land-management interventions (e.g., prioritising fire or fuel breaks in high-risk land-cover types). The following sections interpret the spatial predictions from each fitted LGCP model and consider how these patterns relate to real-world fire risk in GB.

5.1.1 Interpretation of Spatial Field-Only Model

The spatial field-only LGCP (Model 1) produced a plausible and interpretable estimate of fire intensity across Great Britain (GB). Summing the posterior mean intensity over land yields an expected total of approximately **21,227** fires, compared with **67** observed detections in the modelling subset. This discrepancy is not unexpected: satellite-based detection systems such as MODIS are known to under-report fires in temperate regions due to cloud cover, short burn durations, and low-intensity events (Parente et al., 2023; Rodrigues et al., 2018; Giglio, Schroeder, and Justice, 2016). Given the six-month observation window and known under-detection, we

treat Model 1 primarily as a *relative* risk surface rather than an estimate of absolute counts.

The predicted surface captures regional patterns consistent with previous research. Elevated intensities occur across East Anglia, the South East, and parts of the East Midlands (Figure 4.6), areas dominated by arable and grassland habitats and previously associated with higher fire frequencies (Davies and Legg, 2016). Predicted intensity is lower in Scotland and Wales despite extensive fire-prone uplands, which may reflect lower ignition pressure, fewer detection opportunities, or genuine regional differences in incidence.

Predictive uncertainty for Model 1 is high across land pixels (Figure 4.10; Table 4.6). The median CV is 3.781 (IQR 3.411–4.390), with 0% of pixels having CV < 1. Absolute uncertainty shows the same spatial pattern (Figure 4.11; Table 4.7). The median 95% credible-interval width is 1,869.368 fires km⁻² (IQR 354.915–13,065.029; P90 23,595.026, P99 45,680.358), with the largest intervals concentrated in parts of the south and east. Posterior hyperparameters (Table 4.8)—range median 314,589 m (95% CI 197,287–514,811 m) and field SD median 2.181 on the log scale (95% CI 1.562–3.054)—indicate a broadly correlated but high-variance latent field. Accordingly, absolute rates should be interpreted cautiously, and the map is most reliable for relative contrasts and broad hotspots.

Because the spatial field-only model derives its structure directly from the observed point pattern, it avoids assumptions about specific fire–environment relationships. It identifies latent spatial structure that may indicate areas of elevated fire risk even when covariate effects are weak or uncertain. This makes it a valuable baseline for comparison with more complex formulations and a robust reference surface for assessing the added value of environmental predictors.

In summary, Model 1 yields a spatially coherent and ecologically plausible GB fire-risk surface. While the absolute magnitude of predicted fires is influenced by detection bias and model behaviour, the spatial patterns align with the known geography of GB fires and offer meaningful insights for risk assessment and future modelling work.

5.1.2 Interpretation of Land Cover-Only Model

The land cover-only LGCP (Model 2) produced a nearly flat *relative* intensity surface across Great Britain (GB; modelling subset $n = 67$). The mapped pattern (Figure 4.7) is visually uniform and the estimated class effects are close to zero, with 95% credible intervals overlapping zero (Table 4.3). These results indicate that, in this formulation, land cover alone did not provide strong predictive signal for spatial variation in detections across GB; however, this should not be interpreted as evidence that land cover has no influence on fire risk. *Cf.*

Two main factors likely contributed to the weak effects. First, land cover was represented categorically as the dominant class within each 1 km² grid cell in the UKCEH LCM2023 aggregate dataset. Each pixel was thus assigned a single label, even when it contained a heterogeneous mix of habitat types. This simplification may have obscured ecologically relevant variation in fuels and land management. Using continuous class *proportions* per cell (or composition within a local neighbourhood) could better capture fine-scale heterogeneity, but would require substantially greater data processing and computation in a national point process model. Second, MODIS

detection limitations may disproportionately affect certain land-cover types. In heterogeneous or remote landscapes (e.g., shrubland, heathland, moorland), smaller or lower-intensity fires are less likely to be detected; as a result, these habitats may appear less fire-prone in the model than they are in reality.

Ecological and observational evidence nonetheless suggests that land cover can influence fire occurrence in the UK. In southern Europe, wildfires are often associated with agricultural/herbaceous land and urban–rural transition zones (Rodrigues et al., 2018; Parente et al., 2023). In Scottish Fire and Rescue Service records, wildfires frequently occur in upland moorland, heathland, and grassland, particularly near the rural–urban fringe (Davies and Legg, 2016); fires are also documented in young conifer plantations and along forest edges, especially during dry periods or active land management (Legg and Davies, 2007).

Predictive uncertainty for Model 2 is uniformly small across land pixels (Figure 4.12; Table 4.9). The median CV was **0.008** (IQR **0.000–0.008**), and **100%** of pixels had $CV < 1$. Absolute uncertainty was likewise minimal (Figure 4.13; Table 4.10), with a median 95% CI width of **0.029** fires km^{-2} (Q1–Q3 **0.000–0.030**). These narrow intervals reflect that the displayed predictions are driven by class-level fixed effects estimated with high precision when pooled across pixels, because the map excludes the latent spatial field (used only during fitting). Posterior hyperparameters are provided for completeness in Table 4.11.

In summary, the lack of detectable land-cover effects in Model 2 likely reflects a combination of coarse covariate representation and satellite detection bias, rather than a genuine absence of relationship. While this model offered limited explanatory power on its own, it provides a useful baseline for assessing whether environmental covariates add value relative to the spatial field–only and combined models in this GB-only analysis.

5.1.3 Interpretation of Full Model

The combined LGCP (Model 3) incorporated both the spatial field and categorical land-cover covariates, and it predicted substantially higher overall fire intensity than either individual component model. In keeping with Chapter 4, I clipped predictions at the **70th percentile** of the posterior log-intensity distribution (log threshold ≈ 2.62 , equivalent to ≈ 13.74 fires km^{-2}) prior to exponentiation to stabilise the colour scale and avoid numerical overflow (Figure 4.8). The resulting map emphasises *relative* spatial contrasts rather than absolute counts.

Under this 70th-percentile clipping, the *mean* predicted intensity across valid GB land pixels was **11.26** fires km^{-2} (median and quartiles at the clip, 13.79), yielding a summed total of **2,590,262** predicted fires over land (valid pixels $n = 230,039$). This greatly exceeds the $n = 67$ observed detections in the modelling subset, reflecting both the heavy right tail of the latent log-intensity and the mismatch between model scale and sparse detections.

Two factors likely contribute to the inflated scale. *Statistically*, adding land-cover effects to the spatial field can steepen the linear predictor in localised areas, generating very large log-intensity values for a small set of cells (see the heavy upper tail in Figure 4.8). *Structurally*, restricting prediction to terrestrial pixels constrains the GRF to operate entirely within the land mask; extreme field excursions that fell offshore

in the spatial-field-only model (and were thus immaterial) are forced onto land in Model 3, concentrating inflated intensities within the analysis region.

Despite scale inflation, the spatial structure is ecologically plausible and consistent with the data: highest relative intensities occur in eastern and southern England (agricultural and peri-urban areas), with lower values in upland and northern regions (Scotland and Wales). These broad contrasts closely mirror the spatial field-only surface, indicating that the spatial random effect continues to dominate model structure even with covariates included.

Uncertainty for Model 3 is reported primarily as the posterior standard deviation of the log-intensity, $\text{sd}(\log \tilde{\lambda})$, which is stable under exponentiation and comparable across space (Figure 4.14; Table 4.12). Across land pixels, $\text{sd}(\log \tilde{\lambda})$ had median **15.990** (IQR **15.008–17.012**), with **P90 = 18.032** and **P99 = 19.844**. For transparency we also show a 95% credible-interval width map on the intensity scale with a P90 colour-scale clip (Figure 4.15); the *unclipped* distribution (Table 4.13) is dominated by extremes (median $\approx 6.65 \times 10^{28}$ fires km^{-2} ; P90 3.41×10^{154} ; P99 2.17×10^{269} ; 51 non-finite values), illustrating how exponentiation inflates the tail. Posterior hyperparameters (Table 4.14)—range median **30,693** m (95% CI **30,611–30,744** m) and field SD median **18.030** on the log scale (95% CI **18.006–18.046**)—are consistent with a short-range, high-variance latent field. Accordingly, we rely on $\text{sd}(\log \tilde{\lambda})$ as the comparative uncertainty metric and treat intensity-scale CI widths as supplementary.

In summary, Model 3 demonstrates both the strengths and limitations of combining spatial fields with environmental covariates in an LGCP framework. While the spatial patterns align with ecological expectations and observed detections, the absolute fire counts require cautious interpretation. Potential remedies include extending covariates beyond the coastline (e.g., buffer or imputed offshore zones so that extreme field excursions are not forced inland), stronger or alternative PC priors on the spatial field, or field re-parameterisations (e.g., barrier/SPDE formulations) to limit extreme excursions within the analysis region (Simpson et al., 2017).

5.2 Conclusion

This study applied a log–Gaussian Cox process (LGCP) to satellite-detected wildfire occurrence across *Great Britain (GB)* using MODIS active-fire data and categorical land-cover covariates. The modelling subset comprised $n = 67$ detections (confidence $> 65\%$), and we interpret all maps as *relative intensity* surfaces (Chapter 4.3).

Taken together, the three model variants tell a consistent story. A latent spatial field is essential for revealing coherent hotspots—most clearly in southern and eastern England—even when ignition data are sparse. By contrast, land-cover fixed effects alone add little signal at the 1 km dominant-class resolution used here. When combined, the spatial field remains the main driver of pattern, but the absolute scale of intensity can inflate; hence totals are treated cautiously and uncertainty is summarised primarily on the log-scale.

These results have two immediate implications. First, for operational use, the products are most informative as *relative risk* layers for prioritising training, patrols and fuel-break planning, not as absolute counts. Second, improving covariates—notably

proportional land-cover composition and human-activity proxies—together with structural controls (e.g., stronger PC priors, offshore covariate buffers, or barrier/SPDE variants) will be key to calibrating the intensity scale.

Finally, MODIS under-detection in temperate GB means small, short-lived fires are likely missed. Our choice to filter to confidence $> 65\%$ and to report log-scale uncertainty aligns with that reality; future threshold/weighting sensitivity analyses should clarify how detection quality propagates into the spatial surfaces (see uncertainty diagnostics in Chapter 4.3).

In sum, this dissertation establishes a GB-wide, relative wildfire-risk surface using an LGCP fitted with INLA/inlabru and sets a clear path to greater ecological realism and operational utility through richer covariates, stronger scale control, and multi-season extensions.

5.2.1 Future Work and Extensions

Future work can build on this GB-wide analysis in several directions. A first priority is to broaden the response beyond point detections by incorporating *burned area* products. Burned area provides spatially contiguous information on extent and severity and could be used either as an alternative response (e.g., area burned per cell) or as a covariate that helps explain variation in ignition and spread. This would better align inference with ecologically meaningful outcomes than relying solely on instantaneous hotspots.

Applying the framework across multiple fire seasons would increase sample size (the modelling subset here used $n = 67$ detections after confidence filtering) and allow assessment of interannual variability and trends. Combining multi-season data with dynamic covariates—such as fuel moisture, weather, and human activity—would support spatio-temporal prediction while retaining the relative-intensity interpretation emphasised in this dissertation.

A non-exhaustive set of extensions includes:

- **Data integration: burned area and higher-resolution sensors.** Fuse MODIS with complementary sources (e.g., VIIRS active fire at 375 m, Sentinel-2 burned-area products) to improve spatial detail and coverage. Where feasible, harmonise sensor footprints and timing to reduce mismatches between detections and covariates.
- **Explicit observation model and confidence handling.** Treat satellite detections as a *thinned* point process with detection probability depending on conditions (cloud, overpass, fuel/land cover, day/night), and use detection confidence either as a weight or a covariate. Threshold- and weight-sensitivity analyses can quantify how detection quality propagates into risk surfaces.
- **Refining land-cover representation.** Replace the dominant 1 km class with proportional composition (per cell) or use local buffers around points to capture habitat heterogeneity and edge effects (e.g., plantation edges, rural–urban fringe). This keeps the fixed effects interpretable while reducing categorical coarsening.
- **Human-activity proxies.** Include covariates that proxy ignition pressure in GB: distance to settlements/roads/rail, access points and popular recreation areas, national parks and protected sites, and calendar effects (school/bank

holidays, weekends). These can be entered as smooth functions or binned contrasts.

- **Climatic and environmental drivers.** Add wind speed/direction, air temperature, drought and fuel-moisture indicators, recent rainfall deficits, and simple topographic metrics (elevation, slope, aspect). Dynamic drivers can be lagged to reflect preconditioning.
- **Coastline-aware spatial structure and scale control.** Use barrier/SPDE variants or extend covariates into a modest offshore buffer so extreme latent-field excursions are not forced onto land. Consider stronger or alternative PC priors to temper heavy tails and improve absolute-scale calibration.
- **Spatio-temporal models.** Move from a purely spatial LGCP to a spatio-temporal formulation (e.g., seasonal random effects, AR(1) or RW structures in time, or a separable space–time GRF). Pooling multiple seasons aids estimation and stabilises uncertainty while preserving within-season contrasts.
- **Validation and calibration.** Adopt block cross-validation (spatial and spatio-temporal) and proper scoring rules (log score, CRPS) to compare model families. Use posterior predictive checks to assess tail behaviour and, where absolute counts matter, explore normalisation or constraint strategies that align the integrated intensity with observed event totals.

Together, these steps would move GB wildfire modelling towards an operational, decision-support capability: richer covariates to capture fuels and ignition pressure, explicit handling of detection processes, coastline-aware spatial structure to control extremes, and spatio-temporal pooling to increase power and reduce uncertainty. The resulting maps should continue to be read primarily as *relative risk* layers, with absolute calibration introduced cautiously and transparently.

Appendix A

Raw Model Outputs

FIGURE A.1: Raw posterior mean intensity surface predicted by the LGCP model. Values are on the model's original scale (unitless), prior to rescaling to fires per km^2 .

FIGURE A.2: Raw predicted log-intensity surface from the full LGCP model (land cover + spatial field). Values represent log fire intensity before rescaling or clipping.

FIGURE A.3: Model 3 (full): *Uncropped* 95% credible-interval width for predicted intensity λ (fires km^{-2}), land pixels only. The colour scale is not clipped and is dominated by a small number of extreme cells caused by exponentiating heavy-tailed log-intensity predictions. For interpretability, the main text presents $\text{sd}(\log \lambda)$ as the primary uncertainty metric (Figure 4.14) and a P90 colour-scale-clipped CI-width map (Figure 4.15); numerical summaries use uncapped values (Table 4.13).

Appendix B

Full R Code for LGCP Model

LISTING B.1: Complete R script used for model fitting and prediction.

```
set.seed(13)

packages <- c("INLA", "inlabru", "sf", "sp", "rnaturalearth", "
  dplyr", "raster", "ggspatial", "ggplot2", "viridis", "
  tidyverse", "MASS", "knitr")
purrr::map(packages, library, character.only = TRUE)

# Load FIRMS data and remove Northern Ireland (NI) points
firms_df <- read.csv("fire_archive_M-C61_628685.csv")
# Keep only non zero confidence first
firms_df <- subset(firms_df, confidence > 0)

# Exclude NI using a tighter bounding box (lon in [-8.2, -5.4],
  lat in [54.0, 55.5])
firms_df <- subset(
  firms_df,
  !(longitude > -8.2 & longitude < -5.4 & latitude > 54.0 &
    latitude < 55.5)
)

firms_df <- subset(firms_df, confidence > 0) # Drop 0%
  confidence
# Check structure and basic summaries
str(firms_df)
summary(firms_df)
table(firms_df$confidence)

# Assuming confidence > 0 filter already applied monthly counts
  for now thank you
firms_df$month <- format(as.Date(firms_df$acq_date), "%Y-%m") #
  Extract year-month

# Count number of detections per month
monthly_counts <- table(firms_df$month)

# ---- Monthly counts barplot (no title, tidy ticks) ----
y <- monthly_counts

# Month labels -> "Apr", "May", ...
labs <- if (!is.null(names(y))) {
  m <- suppressWarnings(as.integer(substr(names(y), 6, 7)))
```

```

  if (all(!is.na(m))) month.abb[m] else names(y)
} else seq_along(y)

yt <- pretty(c(0, max(y, na.rm = TRUE)))
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 1.6, 1) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7, 0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

barplot(
  y,
  names.arg = labs,
  las = 1, # horizontal month labels
  cex.names = 0.95,
  col = "firebrick",
  border = NA,
  xlab = "Month",
  ylab = "Number of detections",
  ylim = c(0, top),
  yaxs = "i",
  yaxt = "n",
  main = "" # <-- no in-plot title
)
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

# Save exactly this plot
dev.print(png, file = "monthly_fires.png", width = 800, height =
  600, res = 150)

# --- Confidence histogram (no clipping) ---
conf_q <- quantile(firms_df$confidence, probs = c(0.25, 0.5,
  0.75), na.rm = TRUE)

brks <- seq(0, 100, by = 5)
h <- hist(firms_df$confidence, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5)
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
  0)) # more top/right room
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

hist(firms_df$confidence,
  breaks = brks, xlim = c(0,100), ylim = c(0, top),
  yaxs = "i", yaxt = "n", yaxt = "s",
  main = "", xlab = "Confidence (%)",
  col = "lightblue", border = "white")
axis(1, at = seq(0, 100, by = 20))

abline(v = conf_q, col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lwd = 2, lty =
  2)

par(xpd = NA) # allow drawing into margin if needed
legend("topright",
  inset = c(0.02, 0.02), # nudge away
  from edges

```

```

    legend = c("1st_Quartile", "Median", "3rd_Quartile"),
    col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n
        ", cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

# save exactly what you see
dev.print(png, file = "hist_confidence.png", width = 800, height
    = 600, res = 150)

# --- Brightness histogram (no title, tidy axes, save) ---
bright_q <- quantile(firms_df$brightness, probs = c(0.25, 0.5,
    0.75), na.rm = TRUE)

brks <- seq(300, 370, by = 5) # 5 K
bins
h <- hist(firms_df$brightness, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5) # y ticks
    every 5
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
    0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

hist(
  firms_df$brightness,
  breaks = brks,
  xlim = c(300, 370),
  ylim = c(0, top),
  yaxs = "i",
  xaxt = "n", yaxt = "n",
  main = "",
  xlab = "Brightness_temperature_(K)",
  ylab = "Frequency",
  col = "lightblue",
  border = "white"
)
axis(1, at = seq(300, 370, by = 10))
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

abline(v = bright_q, col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lwd = 2, lty
    = 2)

par(xpd = NA) # allow drawing into the right/top margin if
    needed
legend("topright",
    inset = c(0.02, 0.02),
    legend = c("1st_Quartile", "Median", "3rd_Quartile"),
    col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n
        ", cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

# Save exactly this plot
dev.print(png, file = "hist_brightness.png", width = 800, height
    = 600, res = 150)

```

```

# x = firms_df$bright_t31
x <- firms_df$bright_t31
bright31_q <- quantile(x, probs = c(0.25, 0.5, 0.75), na.rm =
  TRUE)

# Align ticks, limits, and bins
x_start <- floor(min(x, na.rm = TRUE) / 5) * 5
x_end <- ceiling(max(x, na.rm = TRUE) / 5) * 5
x_ticks <- seq(x_start, x_end, by = 5)
brks <- seq(x_start, x_end, by = 2) # 2 K bins
h <- hist(x, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
  0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

hist(x, breaks = brks,
  xlim = c(x_start, x_end), ylim = c(0, max(yt)),
  yaxs = "i", xaxt = "n", yaxt = "n",
  main = "", xlab = "Brightness_ttemperature_(K)", ylab = "
    Frequency",
  col = "lightblue", border = "white")
axis(1, at = x_ticks)
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

abline(v = bright31_q, col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lwd = 2,
  lty = 2)

par(xpd = NA)
legend("topright", inset = c(0.02, 0.02),
  legend = c("1st_Quartile", "Median", "3rd_Quartile"),
  col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n",
  cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

dev.print(png, file = "hist_temp.png", width = 800, height =
  600, res = 150)

# --- 1. Read shapefiles using provided file paths ---
eng_regions <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Regions_December_2023_Boundaries_EN_BUC_
  9038152234149124948/RGN_DEC_2023_EN_BUC.shp")
uk_countries <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Countries_December_2022_UK_BGC_
  3062977961700027093/CTRY_DEC_2022_UK_BGC.shp")

# --- 2. Transform all to British National Grid (EPSG:27700) ---
eng_regions <- st_transform(eng_regions, 27700)
uk_countries <- st_transform(uk_countries, 27700)

# --- 3. Extract Wales & Scotland, add region column to all ---
eng_regions <- eng_regions %>% mutate(region = RGN23NM) %>%
  dplyr::select(region, geometry)

```

```

wales_poly <- uk_countries %>% filter(CTRY22NM == "Wales")
  %>% mutate(region = "Wales") %>% dplyr::select(region,
  geometry)
scotland_poly <- uk_countries %>% filter(CTRY22NM == "Scotland")
  %>% mutate(region = "Scotland") %>% dplyr::select(region,
  geometry)

# --- 4. Combine all into a single regions layer ---
all_regions <- rbind(eng_regions, wales_poly, scotland_poly)

# --- 5. Convert fire detections to sf points (WGS84 -> BNG) ---
firepoints_regjoin <- st_as_sf(firms_df, coords = c("longitude",
  "latitude"), crs = 4326)
firepoints_regjoin <- st_transform(firepoints_regjoin, 27700)

# --- 6. Spatial join: assign region to each fire point ---
firepoints_regjoin <- st_join(firepoints_regjoin, all_regions["
  region"])

# --- 7. Drop geometry for summary ---
firepoints_regjoin_df <- st_drop_geometry(firepoints_regjoin)

# --- 8. Summarise stats by region ---
summary_by_region <- firepoints_regjoin_df %>%
  group_by(region) %>%
  summarise(
    n_fires = n(),
    conf_median = median(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    conf_IQR = IQR(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    bright_median = median(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    bright_IQR = IQR(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    temp_median = median(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
    temp_IQR = IQR(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

# --- 9. View summary table ---
print(summary_by_region)

summary_by_region_table <- firepoints_regjoin_df %>%
  group_by(region) %>%
  summarise(
    n_fires = n(),
    brightness_min = min(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    brightness_25 = quantile(brightness, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    brightness_median = median(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    brightness_mean = mean(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    brightness_75 = quantile(brightness, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    brightness_max = max(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),

    confidence_min = min(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    confidence_25 = quantile(confidence, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    confidence_median = median(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    confidence_mean = mean(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    confidence_75 = quantile(confidence, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    confidence_max = max(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
  )

```

```

temp_min = min(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
temp_25 = quantile(bright_t31, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
temp_median = median(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
temp_mean = mean(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
temp_75 = quantile(bright_t31, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
temp_max = max(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE)
)

# Check names and count
print(names(summary_by_region_table))
print(ncol(summary_by_region_table))

# Only do this next step if the length is exactly 20 and the
  order is right
colnames(summary_by_region_table) <- c(
  "Region", "Fires",
  "Brightness_Min", "Brightness_25%", "Brightness_Median", "
  Brightness_Mean", "Brightness_75%", "Brightness_Max",
  "Confidence_Min", "Confidence_25%", "Confidence_Median", "
  Confidence_Mean", "Confidence_75%", "Confidence_Max",
  "Temp_Min", "Temp_25%", "Temp_Median", "Temp_Mean", "Temp_75%"
  , "Temp_Max"
)

# Print as LaTeX table (for PDF or .tex output)
knitr::kable(summary_by_region_table, format = "latex", booktabs
  = TRUE, digits = 2, caption = "Summary_statistics_for_FIRMS
  fire_detections_by_UK_region.")
library(knitr)
latex_code <- knitr::kable(summary_by_region_table, format = "
  latex", booktabs = TRUE, digits = 2, caption = "Summary_
  statistics_for_FIRMS_fire_detections_by_UK_region.")
cat(latex_code, sep = "\n")

firms <- firms_df %>% filter(confidence > 65)

firms_sf <- st_as_sf(firms, coords = c("longitude", "latitude"),
  crs = 4326)
firms_proj <- st_transform(firms_sf, 27700)
coords <- st_coordinates(firms_proj)
firms_df <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2])
coordinates(firms_df) <- ~ x + y
proj4string(firms_df) <- CRS("EPSG:27700")

uk_countries <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Countries_December_2022_UK_BGC_
  3062977961700027093/CTRY_DEC_2022_UK_BGC.shp")

# Filter to just Great Britain
gb <- subset(uk_countries, CTRY22NM %in% c("England", "Scotland"
  , "Wales"))

# Plot to confirm
plot(st_geometry(gb))
plot(st_geometry(firms_proj), add = TRUE, col = "red", pch = 20)

```

```

saveRDS(gb, "gb_boundary_ons.rds")

# Save image to local machine
png("gb_boundary_ons.png", width = 700, height = 900, res = 150)
plot(st_geometry(gb))
plot(st_geometry(firms_proj), add = TRUE, col = "red", pch = 20)
dev.off()

gb_sp <- as(gb, "Spatial")
boundary <- inla.sp2segment(gb_sp)

gb_union <- st_union(gb) # dissolve to one GB polygon
gb_sp <- as(gb_union, "Spatial") # convert to Spatial
boundary <- inla.sp2segment(gb_sp) # convert to INLA boundary

mesh <- inla.mesh.2d(
  loc      = coordinates(firms_df),
  boundary = boundary,
  max.edge = c(20000, 80000),
  cutoff   = 10000
)

plot(mesh, asp = 1, interior = TRUE)

mesh <- inla.mesh.2d(
  loc      = coordinates(firms_df),
  boundary = boundary,
  max.edge = c(20000, 80000),
  cutoff   = 10000
)

plot(mesh, asp = 1, interior = TRUE)

# THIS is the key line
points(coordinates(firms_df)[, 1], coordinates(firms_df)[, 2],
  col = "red", pch = 20)

pdf("mesh_plot.pdf", width = 7, height = 7)
plot(mesh, asp = 1, interior = TRUE)
points(coordinates(firms_df)[,1],
  coordinates(firms_df)[,2],
  col = "red", pch = 20)
dev.off()

spde <- INLA::inla.spde2.pcmatern(
  mesh = mesh,
  prior.sigma = c(1, 0.01), # P( > 1) = 1 %
  prior.range = c(50000, 0.5) # P(range < 50 km) = 50 %
)
cmp <- coordinates ~ field(coordinates, model = spde)

proj4string(firms_df) <- CRS("EPSG:27700") # Add this!

fit <- lgcp(
  components = cmp,

```

```

data = firms_df, # now safely projected
domain = list(coordinates = mesh))

## Predict spatial intensity

# Create prediction grid
bbox <- mesh$loc[, 1:2]
xrange <- range(bbox[, 1])
yrange <- range(bbox[, 2])
xseq <- seq(xrange[1], xrange[2], length.out = 150)
yseq <- seq(yrange[1], yrange[2], length.out = 150)
pred_grid <- expand.grid(x = xseq, y = yseq)
coordinates(pred_grid) <- ~ x + y
proj4string(pred_grid) <- CRS("EPSG:27700")

# Predict intensity
pred <- predict(fit, newdata = pred_grid, formula = ~ exp(field)
)

# Convert to raster
r_pred <- rasterFromXYZ(cbind(pred_grid@coords, pred$mean))

# Save LGCP raw prediction raster (old method), sized for the
page; clean GB axes in km; no title
png("lgcp_raw_mean.png", width = 6.5, height = 4.5, units = "in"
, res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")

op <- options(scipen = 999)
par(xaxs = "i", yaxs = "i", mar = c(4.5, 5, 1, 5.5) + 0.1)

plot(
  r_pred,
  axes = FALSE,
  xlim = c(0, 700e3),
  ylim = c(0, 1300e3),
  xlab = "Easting, GB (km)",
  ylab = "Northing, GB (km)",
  col = rev(heat.colors(50)),
  zlim = range(pred$mean, na.rm = TRUE),
  main = ""
)

axis(1, at = seq(0, 700e3, by = 100e3), labels = seq(0, 700, by
= 100))
axis(2, at = seq(0, 1300e3, by = 250e3), labels = seq(0, 1300,
by = 250), las = 1)
box()

dev.off()
options(op)

# Ensure gb_sp exists (if not already created earlier)
gb_sp <- as(gb, "Spatial") # 'gb' is Great Britain sf object

# Crop and mask the raster to GB boundary
r_cropped <- raster::crop(r_pred, gb_sp)
r_clipped <- raster::mask(r_cropped, gb_sp)

```

```

# Convert to data frame for ggplot
r_df <- as.data.frame(r_clipped, xy = TRUE)
colnames(r_df) <- c("x", "y", "Intensity")
r_df <- r_df[!is.na(r_df$Intensity), ]

# Convert GB boundary to sf for ggplot
gb_sf <- st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# Plot with perceptually uniform viridis scale
ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = Intensity))
  +
  scale_fill_viridis_c(trans = "log10") +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.3) +
  coord_sf(crs = 27700) +
  labs(
    title = "Predicted fire intensity (LGCP)",
    x = "Easting",
    y = "Northing"
  ) +
  theme_minimal()

str(pred)
summary(pred$mean)

# Calculate cell area in m
cell_area <- prod(res(r_clipped)) # resolution = cell width
  height in metres

# Convert predicted intensity from per m to per km
r_km2 <- r_clipped / cell_area * 1e6 # 1e6 m = 1 km

# Plot the raster
plot(r_km2,
  main = "Clipped Fire Intensity (fires per km )",
  col = rev(heat.colors(50)))

# Add GB boundary outline
plot(gb_sp, add = TRUE, border = "black", lwd = 0.8)

# Raster -> data frame
r_df <- as.data.frame(r_km2, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df) <- c("x", "y", "fires_km2")
r_df <- r_df[is.finite(r_df$fires_km2), ]

# Boundary as sf
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# Build plot (no in-plot title; curved lat/long grid; degree
  tick labels)
p <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = fires_km2),
    interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.4) +

```

```

scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)), name = "
  Fires_per_km ",
                    breaks = pretty(range(r_df$fires_km2), n
                                     = 5)) +

coord_sf(
  crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
  xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
) +
labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
theme(
  plot.title = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
                                   = 0.3),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

print(p) # draw on-screen

# Save using the old method (re-render to file)
png("lgcp_predicted_intensity.png", width = 6.5, height = 9,
    units = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

# Summarise values from the raster (fires per km )
intensity_summary <- summary(values(r_km2))
total_expected_fires <- sum(values(r_km2), na.rm = TRUE)

# Format and display table
kable(
  data.frame(
    Statistic = c(
      "Minimum", "1st_Quartile", "Median", "Mean",
      "3rd_Quartile", "Maximum", "Missing(masked)",
      "Total_expected_fires(sum_over_land)"
    ),
    Value = c(
      round(intensity_summary["Min."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["1st_Qu."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Median"], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Mean"], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["3rd_Qu."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Max."], 2),
      intensity_summary["NA's"],
      round(total_expected_fires, 1)
    )
  ),
  caption = "Posterior_mean_fire_intensity(fires_per_km )_
    across_Great_Britain"
)

# Load the GB land cover raster (1km aggregated classes)

```

```

LC_path <- "C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_FIRE_M-C61_
628685/data.landcover.2023/lcm-2023-1km_6023459/aggregate_
class/gb2023lcm1km_dominant_aggregate.tif"
LC_dom <- terra::rast(LC_path)

# Check projection (should be EPSG:27700)
terra::crs(LC_dom)

# Basic plot of the GB-only land cover raster
plot(LC_dom,
     main = "2023_Dominant_Land_Cover_(1 km , Great Britain only)",
     col = viridis(10),
     axes = TRUE,
     legend = FALSE)

# Define the mapping from 1-10 aggregated classes (AC
  Identifiers)
agg_classes <- c(
  "1" = "Broadleaf_woodland",
  "2" = "Coniferous_woodland",
  "3" = "Arable",
  "4" = "Improved_grassland",
  "5" = "Semi-natural_grassland",
  "6" = "Mountain, heath and bog",
  "7" = "Saltwater",
  "8" = "Freshwater",
  "9" = "Coastal",
  "10" = "Built-up areas and gardens"
)

# Convert merged raster to dataframe for ggplot
lc_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
names(lc_df)[3] <- "code"

# Filter only values in 1:10 (aggregated classes)
lc_df <- lc_df[lc_df$code %in% 1:10, ]

# Assign labels
lc_df$label <- factor(agg_classes[as.character(lc_df$code)],
                     levels = agg_classes)

# Plot
ggplot(lc_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = label)) +
  geom_raster() +
  coord_equal() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(name = "Land cover (aggregated)", option
    = "D") +
  labs(
    title = "2023_Dominant_Land_Cover_(1 km )",
    subtitle = "UKCEH_10-class_aggregated_land_cover_(Great
      Britain+_Northern_Ireland)"
  ) +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "right")

```

```

# Aggregated class labels
agg_lookup <- c(
  "1" = "Broadleaf_woodland",
  "2" = "Coniferous_woodland",
  "3" = "Arable",
  "4" = "Improved_grassland",
  "5" = "Semi-natural_grassland",
  "6" = "Mountain,_heath_and_bog",
  "7" = "Saltwater",
  "8" = "Freshwater",
  "9" = "Coastal",
  "10" = "Built-up_areas_and_gardens"
)

# Raster -> data frame (BNG coords)
lc_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
names(lc_df)[3] <- "code"
lc_df <- lc_df[lc_df$code %in% 1:10, ]
lc_df$label <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(lc_df$code)],
  levels = agg_lookup)

# Boundary as sf
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# Colour palette only: brighter broadleaf green; medium brown
# arable; softer yellow/orange grasslands; deeper purple heath
# /bog; darker grey built-up
col_map <- c(
  "Broadleaf_woodland" = "#2ECC71", # brighter green
  "Coniferous_woodland" = "#006400", # dark green
  "Arable" = "#B77E43", # medium brown/ochre
  "Improved_grassland" = "#F1D54E", # calm yellow
  "Semi-natural_grassland" = "#F39C12", # softer orange
  "Mountain,_heath_and_bog" = "#7A4E9C", # deeper purple
  "Saltwater" = "#1F78B4", # blue
  "Freshwater" = "#A6CEE3", # light blue
  "Coastal" = "#F4C27A", # sand
  "Built-up_areas_and_gardens" = "#6E6E6E" # darker grey
)

# Build plot (BNG draw; curved lat/long grid; degree tick labels
# )
p <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = lc_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = label)) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.4) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = col_map, name = "Land_cover_(
    aggregated)", drop = FALSE) +
  coord_sf(
    crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +

```

```

theme(
  plot.title = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
  legend.position = "right",
  legend.title = element_text(size = 10),
  legend.text = element_text(size = 9),
  legend.key.height = grid::unit(0.45, "cm")
) +
guides(fill = guide_legend(ncol = 1, byrow = FALSE, title.
  position = "top", title.hjust = 0))

print(p)

ggsave("landcover2023_map.pdf", width = 6.5, height = 9, units =
  "in", dpi = 300)

# Make a copy of fire points data
firms_df_lc <- firms_df

# Extract raster land cover codes at fire locations
extracted <- terra::extract(LC_dom, vect(firms_df_lc))

# Check if any NA values (meaning points outside raster extent)
if(any(is.na(extracted[,2]))) {
  warning("Some fire points fall outside the land cover raster
    extent!")
}

# Define land cover class lookup (integer codes      labels)
agg_lookup <- c(
  "1" = "Broadleaf_woodland",
  "2" = "Coniferous_woodland",
  "3" = "Arable",
  "4" = "Improved_grassland",
  "5" = "Semi-natural_grassland",
  "6" = "Mountain_heath_and_bog",
  "7" = "Saltwater",
  "8" = "Freshwater",
  "9" = "Coastal",
  "10" = "Built-up_areas_and_gardens"
)

# Add landcover as a factor column to firms_df_lc
firms_df_lc$landcover <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(
  extracted[,2])],
  levels = agg_lookup)

# Check new column
table(firms_df_lc$landcover, useNA = "ifany")

# 1. Set the reference level to something that exists in fire
data
firms_df_lc$landcover <- relevel(firms_df_lc$landcover, ref = "
  Arable")

```

```

# 2. Explicitly add a 'coordinates' column to the data (INLABru
  needs this!)
firms_df_lc@data$coordinates <- coordinates(firms_df_lc)

# 3. Define component formula
cmp_lc <- coordinates ~
  landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
    hyper = list(prec = list(prior = "pc.prec", param =
      c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
  field(coordinates, model = spde)

# 4. Fit the LGCP model with land cover as a covariate
fit_lc <- lgcp(
  components = cmp_lc,
  data = firms_df_lc,
  domain = list(coordinates = mesh)
)

# 5. Extract and format summary of land cover effects
lc_tab <- as.data.frame(fit_lc$summary.random$landcover)
num_cols <- sapply(lc_tab, is.numeric)
lc_tab[, num_cols] <- lapply(lc_tab[, num_cols], round, 3)

# 6. Display the results as a table
knitr::kable(
  lc_tab,
  caption = "LGCP land-cover effects (relative to Arable)"
)

# End-to-end: compute land-cover-only prediction raster ->
  ggplot map
# (same axes/style as previous maps, no title, legend "Fires per
  km "),
# and save using png()+print()+dev.off() to lc_only_prediction.
  png

# 1) Lookup for aggregated land-cover labels (levels must match
  model)
agg_lookup <- c(
  "1"="Broadleaf woodland", "2"="Coniferous woodland", "3"="Arable
  ", "4"="Improved grassland",
  "5"="Semi-natural grassland", "6"="Mountain, heath and bog", "7"
  ="Saltwater", "8"="Freshwater",
  "9"="Coastal", "10"="Built-up areas and gardens"
)

# 2) Build prediction grid from LC_dom and map to model factor
  levels
grid_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3] <- "code"
grid_df$landcover <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(grid_df$code
  )],
  levels = levels(firms_df_lc$
    landcover))
grid_df <- grid_df[!is.na(grid_df$landcover), ]

```

```

# 3) Predict land-cover-only effect with fitted model
grid_spdf <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  coords = grid_df[, c("x", "y")],
  data = data.frame(landcover = grid_df$landcover),
  proj4string = CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)
lp_lc <- predict(fit_lc, newdata = grid_spdf, formula = ~
  landcover, n.samples = 100)

# 4) Write predictions back to a raster and exponentiate to
  intensity
logint_lc <- rast(LC_dom); values(logint_lc) <- NA_real_
cells <- cellFromXY(logint_lc, grid_df[, c("x", "y")])
values(logint_lc)[cells] <- lp_lc$mean
names(logint_lc) <- "log_intensity"

r_df <- as.data.frame(logint_lc, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
r_df$intensity <- exp(r_df$log_intensity)

# 5) Boundary (sp -> sf) for outline
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# 6) Plot (BNG draw with curved lat/long grid + degree ticks; no
  in-plot title)
p <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = intensity))
  +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(
    colours = c("white", "yellow", "orange", "red"),
    name = "Relative intensity (land cover only)",
    na.value = "grey90"
  ) +
  coord_sf(
    crs = sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326), xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0,
      1300000),
    expand = FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
  theme(
    plot.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
      = 0.3),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
  )

# 7) Save using the reliable method
print(p)
png("lc_only_prediction.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units = "
  in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

```

```

# Land-cover-only prediction as **fires per km ** (includes
  intercept), styled like previous maps,
# and saved reliably via png() + print(p) + dev.off().

# 1) Aggregated land-cover lookup (ensure levels match the model
  )
agg_lookup <- c(
  "1"="Broadleaf_woodland", "2"="Coniferous_woodland", "3"="Arable
    ", "4"="Improved_grassland",
  "5"="Semi-natural_grassland", "6"="Mountain, heath_and_bog", "7"
    ="Saltwater", "8"="Freshwater",
  "9"="Coastal", "10"="Built-up_areas_and_gardens"
)

# 2) Prediction grid from land-cover raster (BNG coords)
grid_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3] <- "code"
grid_df$landcover <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(grid_df$code
  )],
  levels = levels(firms_df_lc$
    landcover))
grid_df <- grid_df[!is.na(grid_df$landcover), ]

grid_spdf <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  coords = grid_df[, c("x", "y")],
  data = data.frame(landcover = grid_df$landcover),
  proj4string = CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)

# 3) Predict land-cover effect; convert to intensity per km2
lp_lc <- predict(fit_lc, newdata = grid_spdf, formula = ~
  landcover, n.samples = 100)

# Intercept mean (fallback for naming)
int_name <- if ("(Intercept)" %in% rownames(fit_lc$summary.fixed
  )) "(Intercept)" else "Intercept"
beta0 <- fit_lc$summary.fixed[int_name, "mean"]

eta_mean <- lp_lc$mean + beta0 # linear
  predictor including intercept
lambda_km2 <- exp(eta_mean) * 1e6 # intensity per
  km2 (LGCP is per m2 1e6 )

# 4) Rasterise predictions
int_r <- rast(LC_dom); values(int_r) <- NA_real_
cells <- cellFromXY(int_r, grid_df[, c("x", "y")])
values(int_r)[cells] <- lambda_km2
names(int_r) <- "fires_km2"

# 5) Data frame for ggplot + GB boundary as sf
r_df_km2 <- as.data.frame(int_r, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# 6) Plot (BNG draw with curved lat/long grid + degree ticks; no
  in-plot title)
p <- ggplot() +

```

```

geom_raster(data = r_df_km2, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = fires_
  km2)) +
geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
  0.4) +
scale_fill_gradientn(
  colours = c("white", "yellow", "orange", "red"),
  name = "Fires_per_km ",
  na.value = "grey90"
) +
coord_sf(
  crs = sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum = sf::st_crs(4326), xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0,
  1300000),
  expand = FALSE
) +
labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
theme(
  plot.title = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

# 7) Save reliably
print(p)
png("lc_only_prediction_km2.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units
  = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

# Assuming:
# - firms_df_lc has coordinates, landcover factor column, and is
  projected
# - mesh and spde are already defined

# 1. Define model components with landcover covariate + spatial
  field
cmp_full <- coordinates ~
  landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
    hyper = list(prec = list(prior = "pc.prec", param =
      c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
  field(coordinates, model = spde)

# 2. Fit LGCP model
fit_full <- lgcp(
  components = cmp_full,
  data = firms_df_lc,
  domain = list(coordinates = mesh)
)

# 3. Create prediction grid (from LC raster)
grid_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3] <- "landcover"

```

```

# Define the mapping: raw raster values to land cover labels
lc_mapping <- c(
  "1" = "Broadleaved_woodland",
  "2" = "Coniferous_woodland",
  "3" = "Arable",
  "4" = "Improved_grassland",
  "5" = "Semi-natural_grassland",
  "6" = "Mountain_heath_and_bog",
  "7" = "Saltwater",
  "8" = "Freshwater",
  "9" = "Coastal",
  "10" = "Built-up_areas_and_gardens"
)

# Convert raster values to factor levels used in the model
grid_df$landcover <- factor(
  lc_mapping[as.character(grid_df$landcover)],
  levels = levels(firms_df_lc$landcover)
)

grid_df$x <- as.numeric(grid_df$x)
grid_df$y <- as.numeric(grid_df$y)

grid_spdf <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  coords = grid_df[, c("x", "y")],
  data = data.frame(landcover = grid_df$landcover),
  proj4string = CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)

# 4. Predict log-intensity including spatial field + covariate
lp_full <- predict(
  fit_full,
  newdata = grid_spdf,
  formula = ~ landcover + field,
  n.samples = 100
)

# 5. Convert prediction to raster
logint_full_raster <- setValues(rast(LC_dom), lp_full$mean)

# 6. Plot with heat color scale
r_df <- as.data.frame(logint_full_raster, xy = TRUE, na.rm =
  TRUE)
colnames(r_df)[3] <- "log_intensity"

ggplot(r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = log_intensity)) +
  geom_raster() +
  scale_fill_gradientn(
    colours = rev(RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(9, "YlOrRd")),
    name = "Log-Intensity"
  ) +
  coord_equal() +
  labs(title = "Predicted_Log-Intensity_(Land_Cover_+_Spatial_
    Field)",
    x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_minimal()

```

```

# PLOT-ONLY (no refit/no re-predict): rework the visual of
# existing r_df (x, y, log_intensity)
# to match prior maps (curved lat/long grid, degree tick labels,
# no in-plot title),
# and save with the reliable png() + print(p) + dev.off() method
.

library(ggplot2)
library(sf)

p <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = log_
    intensity)) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(
    colours = rev(RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(9, "YlOrRd")),
    name = "Log-intensity"
  ) +
  coord_sf(
    crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326), # curved lat/long
    graticule + degree tick labels
    xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000),
    expand = FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
  theme(
    plot.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
      = 0.3),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
  )

print(p)
png("lgcp_full_logintensity.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units
  = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

# Extract raw predicted log-intensity values
log_pred <- lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]

# Summary of log-intensity
log_summary <- summary(log_pred)

# Exponentiate to get predicted intensity (fires per km , since
# raster is 1 km resolution)
intensity <- exp(log_pred)

# Summary of intensity (linear scale)
intensity_summary <- summary(intensity)

# 95th percentile of predicted intensity
intensity_95th <- quantile(intensity, 0.95, na.rm = TRUE)

```

```

# Total expected number of fires across GB (sum of expected
  fires per cell)
total_expected_fires <- sum(intensity, na.rm = TRUE)

# Display all summaries
cat("  Summary of predicted log-intensity (raw):\n")
print(log_summary)

cat("\n  Summary of predicted intensity (fires per km ):\n")
print(intensity_summary)

cat("\n  95th percentile of predicted intensity:\n")
print(intensity_95th)

cat("\n  Total expected fires across GB:\n")
print(round(total_expected_fires, 2))

# Remove NA values
log_pred <- lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]

# Generate quantiles from 0% to 100% in 1% steps
log_quantiles <- quantile(log_pred, probs = seq(0, 1, by = 0.01)
)

# Print nicely
print(round(log_quantiles, 2))
# Zoom in on upper 90-100 % quantiles
tail_quantiles <- quantile(log_pred, probs = seq(0.90, 1, by =
  0.01))
print(round(tail_quantiles, 2))

# Filter for zoom range: log-intensity between 0 and 20
log_pred_zoom <- log_pred[log_pred > 0 & log_pred <= 20]

# Plot refined histogram
hist(
  log_pred_zoom,
  breaks = 100,
  main = "",
  xlab = "Log-Intensity",
  col = "tomato",
  border = "white"
)

# Add reference lines
abline(v = quantile(log_pred, c(0.60, 0.70, 0.80)), col = c("
  blue", "green", "purple"), lty = 2)
legend("topright", legend = c("60%", "70%", "80%"),
  col = c("blue", "green", "purple"), lty = 2, bty = "n")

# Save the zoomed-in log-intensity histogram
png("log_intensity_histogram_trimmed.png", width = 800, height =
  600, res = 120)

```

```

# Plot histogram
hist(log_pred[log_pred > 0 & log_pred <= 20],
     breaks = 100,
     main = "",
     xlab = "Log-Intensity",
     col = "tomato",
     border = "white")

# Add quantile reference lines
abline(v = quantile(log_pred, c(0.60, 0.70, 0.80)), col = c("
  blue", "green", "purple"), lty = 2)
legend("topright", legend = c("60%", "70%", "80%"),
     col = c("blue", "green", "purple"), lty = 2, bty = "n")

dev.off()

# 1. Get raw predicted values
log_pred <- lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]
intensity <- exp(log_pred)

# 2. Create summary table
summary_table <- data.frame(
  Scale = c("Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "
    Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity",
    "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity",
    "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity"),
  Statistic = c("Min", "1st_Quartile", "Median", "Mean", "3rd_
    Quartile", "Max",
    "Min", "1st_Quartile", "Median", "Mean", "3rd_
    Quartile", "Max", "Total_Fires"),
  Value = c(
    round(min(log_pred), 2),
    round(quantile(log_pred, 0.25), 2),
    round(median(log_pred), 2),
    round(mean(log_pred), 2),
    round(quantile(log_pred, 0.75), 2),
    round(max(log_pred), 2),

    round(min(intensity), 2),
    round(quantile(intensity, 0.25), 2),
    round(median(intensity), 2),
    mean(intensity), # likely to be Inf
    round(quantile(intensity, 0.75), 2),
    max(intensity), # likely to be Inf
    sum(intensity, na.rm = TRUE) # total predicted fires
  )
)

print(summary_table)

# Step 1: Extract prediction values
log_pred_full <- lp_full$mean
log_pred_full <- log_pred_full[!is.na(log_pred_full)] # remove
  NA for quantile

```

```

# Step 2: Compute 80th percentile on log scale
log_cap_full <- quantile(log_pred_full, 0.70)

# Step 3: Clamp log prediction vector
log_pred_clipped_full <- pmin(lp_full$mean, log_cap_full)

# Step 4: Exponentiate to get intensity
intensity_clipped_full <- exp(log_pred_clipped_full)

# Step 5: Create raster (fires per km )
r_raster_full <- setValues(rast(LC_dom), intensity_clipped_full)

# Step 6: Mask to GB using raster package for compatibility
r_raster_r_full <- raster::raster(r_raster_full) # convert to
  raster format
r_cropped_full <- raster::crop(r_raster_r_full, gb_sp)
r_masked_full <- raster::mask(r_cropped_full, gb_sp)

# Step 7: Already in km , no need to rescale
r_km2_full <- terra::rast(r_masked_full) # convert back to
  terra if needed

# Step 8: Plot
plot(r_km2_full,
     main = paste0("Fire Intensity (70th percentile clipped at",
                   , round(exp(log_cap_full), 1), " fires/km )"),
     col = rev(heat.colors(50)),
     zlim = c(0, round(exp(log_cap_full), 1)))
plot(gb_sp, add = TRUE, border = "black", lwd = 0.8)

# 70th-percentile clipped intensity map (land cover + field),
  styled like previous maps:
# - no in-plot title
# - BNG draw with curved lat/long graticule and degree tick
  labels
# - legend "Fires per km "
# - save via png() + print(p) + dev.off() to lgcp_fullmap_
  capped80.png

library(sf)
library(ggplot2)

# Raster -> data frame for ggplot
r_df_full <- as.data.frame(r_km2_full, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
names(r_df_full)[3] <- "fires_km2"

# GB outline as sf
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# Upper limit from clip (on natural scale)
cap_val <- exp(log_cap_full)

p <- ggplot() +

```

```

geom_raster(data = r_df_full, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = fires_
  km2)) +
geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
  0.4) +
scale_fill_gradientn(
  colours = rev(heat.colors(50)),
  name = "Fires_per_km ",
  limits = c(0, cap_val),
  oob = scales::squish
) +
coord_sf(
  crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum = sf::st_crs(4326), # curved lat/long grid
  + degree tick labels
  xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000),
  expand = FALSE
) +
labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
theme(
  plot.title = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

print(p)
png("lgcp_fullmap_capped80.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units
  = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

# Extract values from the *full model* raster (fires per km , 1
  km resolution)
vals_full <- as.numeric(values(r_km2_full))

# Get summary stats
summary_km2_full <- summary(vals_full)
total_expected_fires_full <- sum(vals_full, na.rm = TRUE)

# Format and display table
kable(
  data.frame(
    Statistic = c(
      "Minimum", "1st_Quartile", "Median", "Mean",
      "3rd_Quartile", "Maximum_(clipped)", "Missing_(NA)",
      "Total_expected_fires_(over_land)"
    ),
    Value = c(
      round(summary_km2_full["Min."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["1st_Qu."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Median"], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Mean"], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["3rd_Qu."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Max."], 2),

```

```

summary_km2_full["NA's"],
round(total_expected_fires_full, 1)
)
),
caption = "Posterior mean fire intensity (fires per km )
across Great Britain from the full LGCP model (clipped at
70th percentile)"
)

# same model, just add samples to get sd & CIs
pred <- predict(fit, pred_grid, ~ exp(field), n.samples = 1000)

# you'll have:
# pred$mean, pred$sd, pred$q0.025, pred$q0.975
pred$cv <- pred$sd / pmax(pred$mean, 1e-12) # optional:
relative uncertainty

# 1) Build CV raster from predictions
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
cv_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], cv = pred$
cv)
r_cv <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(cv_xyz)
raster::crs(r_cv) <- raster::crs(pred_grid)

# 2) Reproject boundary to match raster CRS and mask
gb_sp_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, raster::crs(r_cv))
r_cv_land <- raster::mask(raster::crop(r_cv, gb_sp_bng), gb_sp_
bng)

# 3) Raster -> data frame (same workflow as mean map)
r_df_cv <- as.data.frame(r_cv_land, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df_cv) <- c("x", "y", "cv")
r_df_cv <- r_df_cv[is.finite(r_df_cv$cv), ]

# 4) Plot and save using existing style
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_cv <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df_cv, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = cv),
  interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)), name = "
CV (sd/mean)",
breaks = pretty(range(r_df_cv$cv), n = 5)
) +
  coord_sf(
  crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
  xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
  theme(

```

```

    plot.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
  )

print(p_cv)

png("lgcp_relative_uncertainty_cv_land.png", width = 6.5, height
    = 9,
    units = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_cv)
dev.off()

# Land mask (TRUE on land, FALSE at sea; no NAs)
gb_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid
)))
ov <- sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng) # data.frame of
  polygon attributes
land_idx <- !is.na(ov[[1]]) # logical vector

# Land-only CV
cv <- pred$cv
keep <- land_idx & is.finite(cv)

cv_stats <- data.frame(
  Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
    "Share_CV<0.5", "Share_CV<1.0", "N_land", "NAs_land"),
  Value = c(
    min(cv[keep], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(cv[keep], 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    median(cv[keep], na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(cv[keep], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(cv[keep], 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    max(cv[keep], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(cv[keep], 0.90, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(cv[keep], 0.99, na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(cv[keep] < 0.5, na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(cv[keep] < 1.0, na.rm = TRUE),
    sum(keep, na.rm = TRUE),
    sum(land_idx & !is.finite(cv), na.rm = TRUE)
  )
)

cv_stats$Value <- round(cv_stats$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(cv_stats,
  align = c("l", "r"),
  caption = "Model 1 Relative uncertainty (CV = sd/mean) over land pixels")

write.csv(cv_stats, "m1_cv_summary.csv", row.names = FALSE)

# Hyperparameters table unchanged

```

```

knitr::kable(fit$summary.hyperpar, digits = 3,
             caption = "Model_1_1_1 SPDE_hyperparameters")

# 1) 95% CI width at each grid point
width95 <- pred$q0.975 - pred$q0.025

# 2) Make a raster from prediction grid + width
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
w_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], width95 =
                    width95)
r_w <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz)
raster::crs(r_w) <- raster::crs(pred_grid)

# 3) Mask to land
gb_sp_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, raster::crs(r_w))
r_w_land <- raster::mask(raster::crop(r_w, gb_sp_bng), gb_sp_
                          bng)

# 4) Raster -> data frame
r_df_w <- as.data.frame(r_w_land, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df_w) <- c("x", "y", "width95")
r_df_w <- r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95), ]

# 5) Plot
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df_w, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = width95),
             interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
          0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)),
                       name = "95% CI width",
                       breaks = pretty(range(r_df_w$width95), n
                                         = 5)) +
  coord_sf(
    crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
  theme(
    plot.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
                                     = 0.3),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
  )

print(p_w)

png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m1.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units =
    "in",
    res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_w)

```

```

dev.off()

w <- r_df_w$width95 # land-only values from masked raster->df
w_stats <- data.frame(
  Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99"),
  Value = round(c(min(w, na.rm=TRUE),
                  quantile(w, 0.25, na.rm=TRUE),
                  median(w, na.rm=TRUE),
                  mean(w, na.rm=TRUE),
                  quantile(w, 0.75, na.rm=TRUE),
                  max(w, na.rm=TRUE),
                  quantile(w, 0.90, na.rm=TRUE),
                  quantile(w, 0.99, na.rm=TRUE)), 3)
)

knitr::kable(w_stats, align=c("l", "r"),
             caption="Model 1 95% CI width (fires km-2)  
over land pixels")

# --- insert these lines just before predicting with fit_lc ---

# Give pred_grid a data slot and add the 'coordinates' column
# expected by field(coordinates, ...)
pred_grid <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  pred_grid,
  data = data.frame(coordinates = sp::coordinates(pred_grid))
)

# Add land-cover factor at grid points with the SAME levels as
# in training
lc_codes <- terra::extract(LC_dom, terra::vect(pred_grid))[, 2]
# integers 1..10
pred_grid$landcover <- factor(
  agg_lookup[as.character(lc_codes)],
  levels = levels(firms_df_lc$landcover) # keeps "Arable" as
  reference
)

# Land-cover only predictions + uncertainty
pred_lc <- predict(fit_lc, pred_grid, ~ exp(landcover), n.
  samples = 1000)
pred_lc$cv <- pred_lc$sd / pmax(pred_lc$mean, 1e-12)
pred_lc$width95 <- pred_lc$q0.975 - pred_lc$q0.025

# Build a raster of CV from pred_lc at pred_grid coords
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
cv_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], cv = pred_
  lc$cv)

r_cv <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(cv_xyz)
raster::crs(r_cv) <- raster::crs(pred_grid)

# Mask to GB land
gb_sp_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, raster::crs(r_cv))

```

```

r_cv_land <- raster::mask(raster::crop(r_cv, gb_sp_bng), gb_sp_bng)

# Raster -> data frame
r_df_cv <- as.data.frame(r_cv_land, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df_cv) <- c("x", "y", "cv")
r_df_cv <- r_df_cv[is.finite(r_df_cv$cv), ]

# Plot
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_cv <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df_cv, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = cv),
             interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
          0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)),
                      name = "CV1(sd/mean)",
                      breaks = pretty(range(r_df_cv$cv), n = 5)
                      ) +
  coord_sf(
    crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
  theme(
    plot.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
    panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
  )

print(p_cv)

png("lgcp_relative_uncertainty_cv_m2.png", width = 6.5, height =
    9, units = "in",
    res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_cv)
dev.off()

# Land mask using GB boundary and prediction points (BNG)
gb_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid
)))
ov <- sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng) # polygon
  overlay
land_idx <- !is.na(ov[, 1]) # TRUE = on land

# Land-only CV vector
cv <- pred_lc$cv
cv_land <- cv[land_idx & is.finite(cv)]

# Summary table (land only)
cv_stats_lc <- data.frame(

```

```

Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
             "Share_CV<0.5", "Share_CV<1.0", "N_land", "NAs_land"),
Value = c(
  min(cv_land, na.rm = TRUE),
  quantile(cv_land, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
  median(cv_land, na.rm = TRUE),
  mean(cv_land, na.rm = TRUE),
  quantile(cv_land, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
  max(cv_land, na.rm = TRUE),
  quantile(cv_land, 0.90, na.rm = TRUE),
  quantile(cv_land, 0.99, na.rm = TRUE),
  mean(cv_land < 0.5, na.rm = TRUE),
  mean(cv_land < 1.0, na.rm = TRUE),
  length(cv_land),
  sum(land_idx & !is.finite(cv), na.rm = TRUE)
)
)

cv_stats_lc$Value <- round(cv_stats_lc$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(cv_stats_lc,
             align = c("l", "r"),
             caption = "Model 2 (land-cover only) Relative uncertainty (CV = sd/mean) over land pixels")

# Hyperparameters table
knitr::kable(fit_lc$summary.hyperpar, digits = 3,
             caption = "Model 2 (land-cover only) Hyperparameters")

# 1) 95% CI width at each grid point
width95 <- pred_lc$q0.975 - pred_lc$q0.025

# 2) Make a raster from prediction grid + width
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
w_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], width95 = width95)
r_w <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz)
raster::crs(r_w) <- raster::crs(pred_grid)

# 3) Mask to land
gb_sp_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, raster::crs(r_w))
r_w_land <- raster::mask(raster::crop(r_w, gb_sp_bng), gb_sp_bng)

# 4) Raster -> data frame
r_df_w <- as.data.frame(r_w_land, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df_w) <- c("x", "y", "width95")
r_df_w <- r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95), ]

# 5) Plot
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w <- ggplot() +

```

```

geom_raster(data = r_df_w, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = width95),
  interpolate = TRUE) +
geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
  0.4) +
scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)),
  name = "95% CI width",
  breaks = pretty(range(r_df_w$width95), n
    = 5)) +
coord_sf(
  crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
  xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
) +
labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
theme(
  plot.title = element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
    = 0.3),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

print(p_w)

png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m2.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units =
  "in",
  res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_w)
dev.off()

# 95% CI width
width95 <- pred_lc$q0.975 - pred_lc$q0.025

# Land mask (BNG)
gb_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid
  )))
ov <- sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng)
land_idx <- !is.na(ov[, 1])

# Land-only vector
w <- width95[land_idx & is.finite(width95)]

# Summary table (land only)
w_stats <- data.frame(
  Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
    "N(land)", "NAs(land)"),
  Value = c(
    min(w, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(w, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    median(w, na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(w, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(w, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    max(w, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(w, 0.90, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(w, 0.99, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    sum(land_idx & is.finite(width95)),
    sum(land_idx & !is.finite(width95))
  )
)

w_stats$Value <- round(w_stats$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(w_stats, align = c("l","r"),
             caption = "Model 2 (land-cover only) 95% CI width (fires km-2) over land pixels")

# optional: save to disk
write.csv(w_stats, "m2_ciwidth_summary.csv", row.names = FALSE)

# Give pred_grid a data slot + 'coordinates' column, and add
# land-cover factor
pred_grid <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(pred_grid,
                                   data = data.frame(
                                     coordinates = sp::
                                       coordinates(pred_grid))
lc_codes <- terra::extract(LC_dom, terra::vect(pred_grid))[,2]
pred_grid$landcover <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(lc_codes)
],
                             levels = levels(firms_df_lc$
landcover))

# Keep land-only and valid land-cover cells
gb_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid)
))
on_land <- !is.na(sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng)[,1])
pg <- pred_grid[on_land & !is.na(pred_grid$landcover), ]

pred_log <- predict(fit_full, pg, ~ landcover + field) #
returns mean & sd for log

coords <- sp::coordinates(pg)
sd_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], sd = pred_
log$sd)

r_sd <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(sd_xyz); raster::crs(r_sd) <-
raster::crs(pg)
r_df_sd <- as.data.frame(r_sd, xy = TRUE); names(r_df_sd) <- c("
x", "y", "sd")
r_df_sd <- r_df_sd[is.finite(r_df_sd$sd), ]

gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)
p_sd <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df_sd, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = sd),
             interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)), name = "
sd(log\u03BB)",
                      breaks = pretty(range(r_df_sd$sd), n = 5)
) +

```

```

coord_sf(crs = sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs = sf::st_crs
(27700),
        datum = sf::st_crs(4326), xlim = c(0,700000), ylim =
        c(0,1300000), expand = FALSE) +
labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") + theme_bw(base_size = 11)

print(p_sd)
png("lgcp_sdlog_map_m3.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units = "
in",
    res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_sd); dev.off()

# Predict log-intensity ( ) on land-only grid
pred_log <- predict(fit_full, pg, ~ landcover + field)

# sd(log ) summary over land pixels
sd_vals <- pred_log$sd

sd_stats_full <- data.frame(
  Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99
", "Nland"),
  Value = c(
    min(sd_vals, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    median(sd_vals, na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(sd_vals, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    max(sd_vals, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals, 0.90, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals, 0.99, na.rm = TRUE),
    sum(is.finite(sd_vals))
  )
)

sd_stats_full$Value <- round(sd_stats_full$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(sd_stats_full,
             align = c("l", "r"),
             caption = "Model3(full) sd(log ) over land
pixels")

# (Optional: save)
write.csv(sd_stats_full, "m3_sdlog_summary.csv", row.names =
FALSE)

# Hyperparameters
knitr::kable(fit_full$summary.hyperpar, digits = 3,
             caption = "Model3(full) Hyperparameters")

# 1) From existing log-scale predictions
# (if needed: pred_log <- predict(fit_full, pg, ~ landcover +
field))
mu <- pred_log$mean
sigma <- pmax(pred_log$sd, 0)

q025 <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.025) * sigma)

```

```

q975    <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.975) * sigma)
width95 <- q975 - q025

# 2) Raster -> df -> ggplot
coords <- sp::coordinates(pg)
w_xyz  <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2], width95 =
  width95)
r_w    <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz); raster::crs(r_w) <-
  raster::crs(pg)

r_df_w <- as.data.frame(r_w, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df_w) <- c("x", "y", "width95")
r_df_w <- r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95), ]

gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df_w, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = width95),
    interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)),
    name = "95% CI width",
    breaks = pretty(range(r_df_w$width95), n
      = 5)) +
  coord_sf(crs = sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs = sf::st_crs
    (27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326), xlim = c(0,700000), ylim =
      c(0,1300000), expand = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11)

print(p_w)
png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m3.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units =
  "in",
  res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_w); dev.off()

# 95% CI width on intensity scale
mu    <- pred_log$mean
sigma <- pmax(pred_log$sd, 0)
q025  <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.025) * sigma)
q975  <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.975) * sigma)
width95 <- q975 - q025

# 90th percentile threshold (land-only grid 'pg')
thr90 <- quantile(width95, 0.90, na.rm = TRUE)
share_clipped <- mean(width95 > thr90, na.rm = TRUE) # for
  caption/log

# Clamp for plotting
coords <- sp::coordinates(pg)
w_xyz  <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2],
  width95_p = pmin(width95, thr90))

# Raster -> df -> ggplot

```

```

r_w <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz); raster::crs(r_w) <-
  raster::crs(pg)
r_df <- as.data.frame(r_w, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df) <- c("x", "y", "width95_p")
r_df <- r_df[is.finite(r_df$width95_p), ]

gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)
p_w <- ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = width95_p),
    interpolate = TRUE) +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
    0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)),
    name = "95% CI width (P90 clip)",
    breaks = pretty(range(r_df$width95_p), n
      = 5)) +
  coord_sf(crs = sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs = sf::st_crs
    (27700),
    datum = sf::st_crs(4326), xlim = c(0,700000), ylim =
      c(0,1300000), expand = FALSE) +
  labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11)

print(p_w)
png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m3_p90.png", width = 6.5, height = 9,
  units = "in",
  res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p_w); dev.off()

# CI width on intensity scale from log-scale summaries
mu <- pred_log$mean
sigma <- pmax(pred_log$sd, 0)

q025 <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.025) * sigma)
q975 <- exp(mu + qnorm(0.975) * sigma)
width95 <- q975 - q025

# Land-only vector (pg is already land-only); keep finite values
for stats
finite <- is.finite(width95)

w_stats_full <- data.frame(
  Statistic = c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
    "N(land)", "Non-finite(land)"),
  Value = round(c(
    min(width95[finite], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(width95[finite], 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    median(width95[finite], na.rm = TRUE),
    mean(width95[finite], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(width95[finite], 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
    max(width95[finite], na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(width95[finite], 0.90, na.rm = TRUE),
    quantile(width95[finite], 0.99, na.rm = TRUE),
    sum(finite),
    sum(!finite)
  ), 3)

```

```
)  
  
knitr::kable(w_stats_full, align = c("l", "r"),  
             caption = "Model 3 (full) 95% CI width (fires  
km-2) over land pixels")  
  
thr90 <- unname(quantile(width95[finite], 0.90, na.rm = TRUE))  
share_clipped <- mean(width95[finite] > thr90)
```


Appendix C

Full R Markdown Script for LGCP Model

LISTING C.1: Complete R Markdown script used for model fitting and prediction.

```

---
title: "INLABru_LGCP_Model_for_FIRMS_GB_Fires_attempting_error_fixes"
output:
  html_document: default
  word_document: default
  pdf_document: default
---

## Introduction

This document fits a Log-Gaussian Cox Process (LGCP) model using the INLABru package to model the spatial intensity of high-confidence fire detections in the GB from FIRMS data. This initial version does not use covariates. The final section includes a ggplot version of the prediction raster clipped to the GB boundary.

## Load required packages

Packages required are INLA, INLABru, sf, sp, rnatralearth, dplyr, raster, ggplot2, and ggspatial. These are used for model fitting, spatial data handling, and visualisation. I load them programmatically using purrr::map to ensure all are available.

```{r load-packages, include=FALSE}
packages <- c("INLA", "inlabru", "sf", "sp", "rnatralearth", "dplyr", "raster", "ggspatial", "ggplot2", "viridis", "tidyverse", "MASS", "knitr")
purrr::map(packages, library, character.only = TRUE)
```

## Exploratory Analysis of data

```{r explore data, echo=FALSE}

Load FIRMS data and remove Northern Ireland (NI) points

```

```

firms_df <- read.csv("fire_archive_M-C61_628685.csv")
Keep only non zero confidence first
firms_df <- subset(firms_df, confidence > 0)

Exclude NI using a tighter bounding box (lon in [-8.2, -5.4],
lat in [54.0, 55.5])
firms_df <- subset(
 firms_df,
 !(longitude > -8.2 & longitude < -5.4 & latitude > 54.0 &
 latitude < 55.5)
)

firms_df <- subset(firms_df, confidence > 0) # Drop 0%
confidence
Check structure and basic summaries
str(firms_df)
summary(firms_df)
table(firms_df$confidence)

Assuming confidence > 0 filter already applied monthly counts
for now thank you
firms_df$month <- format(as.Date(firms_df$acq_date), "%Y-%m") #
Extract year-month

Count number of detections per month
monthly_counts <- table(firms_df$month)

---- Monthly counts barplot (no title, tidy ticks) ----
y <- monthly_counts

Month labels -> "Apr", "May", ...
labs <- if (!is.null(names(y))) {
 m <- suppressWarnings(as.integer(substr(names(y), 6, 7)))
 if (all(!is.na(m))) month.abb[m] else names(y)
} else seq_along(y)

yt <- pretty(c(0, max(y, na.rm = TRUE)))
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 1.6, 1) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7, 0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

barplot(
 y,
 names.arg = labs,
 las = 1, # horizontal month labels
 cex.names = 0.95,
 col = "firebrick",
 border = NA,
 xlab = "Month",
 ylab = "Number of detections",
 ylim = c(0, top),
 yaxs = "i",
 yaxt = "n",
 main = "" # <-- no in-plot title
)
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

```

```

Save exactly this plot
dev.print(png, file = "monthly_fires.png", width = 800, height =
 600, res = 150)

--- Confidence histogram (no clipping) ---
conf_q <- quantile(firms_df$confidence, probs = c(0.25, 0.5,
 0.75), na.rm = TRUE)

brks <- seq(0, 100, by = 5)
h <- hist(firms_df$confidence, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5)
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
 0)) # more top/right room
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

hist(firms_df$confidence,
 breaks = brks, xlim = c(0,100), ylim = c(0, top),
 yaxs = "i", xaxt = "n", yaxt = "s",
 main = "", xlab = "Confidence (%)",
 col = "lightblue", border = "white")
axis(1, at = seq(0, 100, by = 20))

abline(v = conf_q, col = c("red","green","blue"), lwd = 2, lty =
 2)

par(xpd = NA) # allow drawing into margin if needed
legend("topright",
 inset = c(0.02, 0.02), # nudge away
 from edges
 legend = c("1st_Quartile", "Median", "3rd_Quartile"),
 col = c("red","green","blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n",
 cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

save exactly what you see
dev.print(png, file = "hist_confidence.png", width = 800, height
 = 600, res = 150)

--- Brightness histogram (no title, tidy axes, save) ---
bright_q <- quantile(firms_df$brightness, probs = c(0.25, 0.5,
 0.75), na.rm = TRUE)

brks <- seq(300, 370, by = 5) # 5 K
bins
h <- hist(firms_df$brightness, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5) # y ticks
every 5
top <- max(yt)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
 0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

```

```

hist(
 firms_df$brightness,
 breaks = brks,
 xlim = c(300, 370),
 ylim = c(0, top),
 yaxs = "i",
 xaxt = "n", yaxt = "n",
 main = "",
 xlab = "Brightnesstemperature(K)",
 ylab = "Frequency",
 col = "lightblue",
 border = "white"
)
axis(1, at = seq(300, 370, by = 10))
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

abline(v = bright_q, col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lwd = 2, lty
 = 2)

par(xpd = NA) # allow drawing into the right/top margin if
 needed
legend("topright",
 inset = c(0.02, 0.02),
 legend = c("1stQuartile", "Median", "3rdQuartile"),
 col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n",
 cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

Save exactly this plot
dev.print(png, file = "hist_brightness.png", width = 800, height
 = 600, res = 150)

x = firms_df$bright_t31
x <- firms_df$bright_t31
bright31_q <- quantile(x, probs = c(0.25, 0.5, 0.75), na.rm =
 TRUE)

Align ticks, limits, and bins
x_start <- floor(min(x, na.rm = TRUE) / 5) * 5
x_end <- ceiling(max(x, na.rm = TRUE) / 5) * 5
x_ticks <- seq(x_start, x_end, by = 5)
brks <- seq(x_start, x_end, by = 2) # 2 K bins
h <- hist(x, breaks = brks, plot = FALSE)
yt <- seq(0, ceiling(max(h$counts)/5)*5, by = 5)

op <- par(mar = c(4.8, 4.2, 2.0, 2.2) + 0.1, mgp = c(2.0, 0.7,
 0))
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

hist(x, breaks = brks,
 xlim = c(x_start, x_end), ylim = c(0, max(yt)),
 yaxs = "i", xaxt = "n", yaxt = "n",
 main = "", xlab = "Brightnesstemperature(K)", ylab = "
 Frequency",
 col = "lightblue", border = "white")

```

```

axis(1, at = x_ticks)
axis(2, at = yt, labels = yt)

abline(v = bright31_q, col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lwd = 2,
 lty = 2)

par(xpd = NA)
legend("topright", inset = c(0.02, 0.02),
 legend = c("1st_Quartile", "Median", "3rd_Quartile"),
 col = c("red", "green", "blue"), lty = 2, lwd = 2, bty = "n",
 cex = 0.9)
par(xpd = FALSE)

dev.print(png, file = "hist_temp.png", width = 800, height =
 600, res = 150)

...

Regionalise data for tbale extrapolation

```{r regional data, echo=FALSE}
library(sf)
library(dplyr)

# --- 1. Read shapefiles using provided file paths ---
eng_regions <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Regions_December_2023_Boundaries_EN_BUC_
  9038152234149124948/RGN_DEC_2023_EN_BUC.shp")
uk_countries <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Countries_December_2022_UK_BGC_
  3062977961700027093/CTRY_DEC_2022_UK_BGC.shp")

# --- 2. Transform all to British National Grid (EPSG:27700) ---
eng_regions <- st_transform(eng_regions, 27700)
uk_countries <- st_transform(uk_countries, 27700)

# --- 3. Extract Wales & Scotland, add region column to all ---
eng_regions <- eng_regions %>% mutate(region = RGN23NM) %>%
  dplyr::select(region, geometry)
wales_poly <- uk_countries %>% filter(CTRY22NM == "Wales")
  %>% mutate(region = "Wales") %>% dplyr::select(region,
  geometry)
scotland_poly <- uk_countries %>% filter(CTRY22NM == "Scotland")
  %>% mutate(region = "Scotland") %>% dplyr::select(region,
  geometry)

# --- 4. Combine all into a single regions layer ---
all_regions <- rbind(eng_regions, wales_poly, scotland_poly)

# --- 5. Convert fire detections to sf points (WGS84 -> BNG) ---
firepoints_regjoin <- st_as_sf(firms_df, coords = c("longitude",
  "latitude"), crs = 4326)
firepoints_regjoin <- st_transform(firepoints_regjoin, 27700)

# --- 6. Spatial join: assign region to each fire point ---
firepoints_regjoin <- st_join(firepoints_regjoin, all_regions["
  region"])

```

```

# --- 7. Drop geometry for summary ---
firepoints_regjoin_df <- st_drop_geometry(firepoints_regjoin)

# --- 8. Summarise stats by region ---
summary_by_region <- firepoints_regjoin_df %>%
  group_by(region) %>%
  summarise(
    n_fires = n(),
    conf_median = median(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    conf_IQR = IQR(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
    bright_median = median(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    bright_IQR = IQR(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
    temp_median = median(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
    temp_IQR = IQR(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

# --- 9. View summary table ---
print(summary_by_region)

...

## Table for above

```{r summary-table, results='asis', echo=FALSE}
library(dplyr)
library(knitr)

summary_by_region_table <- firepoints_regjoin_df %>%
 group_by(region) %>%
 summarise(
 n_fires = n(),
 brightness_min = min(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
 brightness_25 = quantile(brightness, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
 brightness_median = median(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
 brightness_mean = mean(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),
 brightness_75 = quantile(brightness, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
 brightness_max = max(brightness, na.rm = TRUE),

 confidence_min = min(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
 confidence_25 = quantile(confidence, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
 confidence_median = median(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
 confidence_mean = mean(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),
 confidence_75 = quantile(confidence, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
 confidence_max = max(confidence, na.rm = TRUE),

 temp_min = min(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
 temp_25 = quantile(bright_t31, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
 temp_median = median(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
 temp_mean = mean(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE),
 temp_75 = quantile(bright_t31, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE),
 temp_max = max(bright_t31, na.rm = TRUE)
)

Check names and count
print(names(summary_by_region_table))
print(ncol(summary_by_region_table))

```

```

Only do this next step if the length is exactly 20 and the
 order is right
colnames(summary_by_region_table) <- c(
 "Region", "Fires",
 "Brightness_Min", "Brightness_25%", "Brightness_Median", "
 Brightness_Mean", "Brightness_75%", "Brightness_Max",
 "Confidence_Min", "Confidence_25%", "Confidence_Median", "
 Confidence_Mean", "Confidence_75%", "Confidence_Max",
 "Temp_Min", "Temp_25%", "Temp_Median", "Temp_Mean", "Temp_75%"
 , "Temp_Max"
)

Print as LaTeX table (for PDF or .tex output)
knitr::kable(summary_by_region_table, format = "latex", booktabs
 = TRUE, digits = 2, caption = "Summary_statistics_for_FIRMS
 fire_detections_by_UK_region.")
library(knitr)
latex_code <- knitr::kable(summary_by_region_table, format = "
 latex", booktabs = TRUE, digits = 2, caption = "Summary_
 statistics_for_FIRMS_fire_detections_by_UK_region.")
cat(latex_code, sep = "\n")

...

Load and prepare FIRMS fire detection data

This step loads the FIRMS dataset and keeps only those fires
 that were detected with high confidence. These detections
 are transformed from WGS84 to British National Grid (EPSG
 :27700), and then prepared as a SpatialPoints object for use
 in INLABru.

```{r load-firms, include=FALSE}
firms <- firms_df %>% filter(confidence > 65)

firms_sf <- st_as_sf(firms, coords = c("longitude", "latitude"),
  crs = 4326)
firms_proj <- st_transform(firms_sf, 27700)
coords <- st_coordinates(firms_proj)
firms_df <- data.frame(x = coords[,1], y = coords[,2])
coordinates(firms_df) <- ~ x + y
proj4string(firms_df) <- CRS("EPSG:27700")
```

Plot FIRMS fire locations with GB boundary

This plot gives a quick visual check of where the fire points
 are relative to the GB outline. It helps confirm that the
 projection was done correctly and shows the data coverage
 area.

```{r plot-firms-map, echo=FALSE}
uk_countries <- st_read("C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_
  FIRE_M-C61_628685/Countries_December_2022_UK_BGC_
  3062977961700027093/CTRY_DEC_2022_UK_BGC.shp")

# Filter to just Great Britain

```

```

gb <- subset(uk_countries, CTRY22NM %in% c("England", "Scotland"
, "Wales"))

# Plot to confirm
plot(st_geometry(gb))
plot(st_geometry(firms_proj), add = TRUE, col = "red", pch = 20)

saveRDS(gb, "gb_boundary_ons.rds")

# Save image to local machine
png("gb_boundary_ons.png", width = 700, height = 900, res = 150)
plot(st_geometry(gb))
plot(st_geometry(firms_proj), add = TRUE, col = "red", pch = 20)
dev.off()

...

## Convert GB boundary for mesh construction

The GB boundary (sf) is converted to Spatial and then to `inla.sp2segment`, which is used to constrain the mesh within the GB outline.

```{r convert-boundary, include=FALSE}
gb_sp <- as(gb, "Spatial")
boundary <- inla.sp2segment(gb_sp)
...

Create spatial mesh

This step creates the spatial mesh used to model the underlying latent field. The edge lengths are tuned to the expected fire density and spatial scale of the data. The points help check the overlay.

The mesh is simply a triangular net that INLA lays over the GB so it can store the latent fire-intensity surface at a manageable number of key locations. Each vertex of the net holds one random value; inside every triangle the three corner values are blended linearly, giving a smooth surface everywhere without having to remember a value for every square meter.

To create the net INLA starts with your fire coordinates and the GB coastline, then builds a Delaunay triangulation arrangement that favors broad, well-shaped triangles. It repeatedly checks every edge: if a side on land is longer than the inner max.edge (say 20 km) it drops an extra vertex in the middle and re-ties the triangles; in the offshore buffer it applies the larger outer max.edge (for example 80 km) so the net can be looser where you do not care about detail. If two fire points are closer than the cutoff distance, only one is kept for seeding the triangulation, preventing a tangle of tiny triangles in dense clusters.

```

Choosing the numbers `is` is pragmatic: `set` the inner `max.edge` to roughly one-third to one-half of the `distance` over `which` you believe two locations still `influence` each other (the prior correlation `range`). A larger value coarsens the mesh and speeds computation; a smaller value gives finer detail but costs more `memory` and `time`. Simplifying the coastline with a few-kilometer tolerance before meshing removes unnecessary squiggles that would otherwise force very small coastal triangles.

With the mesh in place INLA assigns a `Mat rn`-type covariance to the vertex values, controlled `by` just two knobs `range` and `varianceso` the `model` can infer a smooth yet flexible fire-intensity surface `while` staying computationally efficient.

`# Vertices`

A vertex `is` simply a knot in the triangular `mesh` the specific geographic point where the `model` stores a `single` latent value (height). Think of the mesh `as` a wire-`frame` blanket: the vertices are the places where the wires cross. By keeping values only at these knots and linearly blending them inside each triangle, the `model` recreates a continuous surface `while` using far fewer numbers than `if` it tried to store a value `for` every pixel `on` the map.

`# Mat rn -type covariance`

`Mat rn` covariance `is` a widely used rule that says `points` closer than about `kilometres` tend to look similar, and similarity fades smoothly beyond that `distance`. It `is` controlled `by` two intuitive parameters: the `range` ( ) sets how quickly correlation drops with `distance`, and the `variance` ( ) sets how tall the surfaces ups-and-downs can be. INLA converts this rule into a sparse precision `matrix on` the `meshs` vertex values, making it possible to fit smooth yet flexible spatial models efficiently.

`# Delaunay triangulation`

Delaunay triangulation `is` the algorithm INLA uses to connect `points` (your fire locations plus coastline vertices) into triangles. Its guiding rule `is`: no triangle should have a very sharp corner. By always choosing the `layout` that maximises the smallest interior angle, it produces fat, well-proportioned triangles rather than long, skinny ones. These well-shaped triangles lead to better numerical stability and a cleaner interpolation of the latent surface across the mesh.

INLA's mesh builder takes your input `points` and links them into a Delaunay triangulation: a pattern of triangles arranged so that the smallest interior angle in the whole mesh is as large as possible. This max -min- angle rule avoids long, needle-thin triangles and gives a well-proportioned, numerically stable `grid`. A plain Delaunay mesh is not necessarily centroidal its vertices are the original `data` and boundary `points`, not the centers (centroids) of the triangles. (A centroidal Voronoi/Delaunay layout would require extra Lloyd iterations that move each vertex to the centre of its surrounding cell; INLA does not perform that step by default.) So, the mesh here is a straight Delaunay triangulation: good angles, but the vertices stay where the `data` and coastline told them to be rather than drifting to centroids.

```

```{r hmmm, echo=FALSE}
gb_union <- st_union(gb)           # dissolve to one GB polygon
gb_sp <- as(gb_union, "Spatial")   # convert to Spatial
boundary <- inla.sp2segment(gb_sp) # convert to INLA boundary
```

```{r create-mesh, echo=FALSE}
set.seed(13)

mesh <- inla.mesh.2d(
  loc      = coordinates(firms_df),
  boundary = boundary,
  max.edge = c(20000, 80000),
  cutoff   = 10000
)

plot(mesh, asp = 1, interior = TRUE)

# THIS is the key line
points(coordinates(firms_df)[, 1], coordinates(firms_df)[, 2],
  col = "red", pch = 20)

pdf("mesh_plot.pdf", width = 7, height = 7); plot(mesh, asp = 1,
  interior = TRUE); points(coordinates(firms_df)[,1],
  coordinates(firms_df)[,2], col = "red", pch = 20); dev.off()

...

## Define model components

Model-component note
inla.spde2.pcmatern() converts the triangle mesh into a latent
Matern Gaussian surface by solving a stochastic PDE on the
mesh. The two PC-prior settings prior.sigma = c(20, 0.01)
and prior.range = c(50000, 0.5) mean there is only a 1 %
chance that the fields marginal standard deviation (sigma
) exceeds 20, and a 50 % chance that the correlation range (
rho) is smaller than 50 km. That keeps the surface from over-
fitting while still letting the data move sigma and rho if
needed.

```

The companion [formula](#)

```
cmp <- coordinates ~ field(coordinates, model = spde)
```

plugs the Mat rn field into the Log-Gaussian Cox Process: at every fire location the [log](#)-intensity [is](#) taken to be the value of this latent surface (plus an intercept that `lgcp()` adds automatically). In short, these two [lines](#) declare what the hidden spatial field [is](#) (Mat rn) and how it links to the observed fire [points](#).

```
```{r define-components, include=FALSE}
set.seed(13)
spde <- INLA::inla.spde2.pcmatern(
 mesh = mesh,
 prior.sigma = c(1, 0.01), # P(> 1) = 1 %
 prior.range = c(50000, 0.5) # P(range < 50 km) = 50 %
)
cmp <- coordinates ~ field(coordinates, model = spde)
```
```

```
## Fit LGCP model
```

Fit the LGCP using `inlabru::lgcp`. The [model](#) assumes [log](#)-Gaussian intensity over space with a [single](#) spatial random effect.

`lgcp()` tells INLABru to fit a Log-Gaussian Cox Process: it treats each fire point [as](#) a Poisson event whose [log](#)-intensity equals the Mat rn field defined in `cmp`. Behind the scenes INLABru builds an [integration stack](#) a dense [grid](#) of pseudo-[points](#) that covers every triangle in the [mesh](#) so the Poisson likelihood can compare where fires occurred with where they could have occurred but didn't. All numerical integration [is](#) done [on](#) the same mesh supplied in domain, so no extra rasters are needed. The result fit contains posterior summaries [for](#) the intercept, the Mat rn hyper-parameters (`rho` and `sigma`), and the random [weights](#) at each mesh vertex, ready [for](#) prediction [or](#) plotting.

```
```{r fit-lgcp, include=FALSE}
set.seed(13)
proj4string(firms_df) <- CRS("EPSG:27700") # Add this!

fit <- lgcp(
 components = cmp,
 data = firms_df, # now safely projected
 domain = list(coordinates = mesh)
)
```
```

```
## Predicting spatial intensity
```

In this chunk we turn the [fitted](#) LGCP into a map.

First we build a 150 x 150 regular `grid` that spans the full extent of the mesh and tag it with the same CRS (EPSG 27700). Then

```
pred <- predict(fit, newdata = pred_grid,
               formula = ~ exp(field))
```

asks INLABru to evaluate the posterior `mean` of `exp(field)` at every `grid` point; the `exp()` converts the latent `log`-field back to an intensity, i.e. expected fires `m`. Finally we wrap the `(x, y, mean)` table into a raster with `rasterFromXYZ()`, making it easy to `plot` or mask with the GB outline. (If you need uncertainty, `add se = TRUE` or draw samples with `predict(..., n.samples = 1000)` to `get` standard-deviation or `quantile` rasters alongside the `mean`.)

```
```{r predict-intensity, echo=FALSE}
set.seed(13)
Predict spatial intensity

Create prediction grid
bbox <- mesh$loc[, 1:2]
xrange <- range(bbox[, 1])
yrange <- range(bbox[, 2])
xseq <- seq(xrange[1], xrange[2], length.out = 150)
yseq <- seq(yrange[1], yrange[2], length.out = 150)
pred_grid <- expand.grid(x = xseq, y = yseq)
coordinates(pred_grid) <- ~ x + y
proj4string(pred_grid) <- CRS("EPSG:27700")

Predict intensity
pred <- predict(fit, newdata = pred_grid, formula = ~ exp(field)
)

Convert to raster
r_pred <- rasterFromXYZ(cbind(pred_grid@coords, pred$mean))

Save LGCP raw prediction raster (old method), sized for the
page; clean GB axes in km; no title
png("lgcp_raw_mean.png", width = 6.5, height = 4.5, units = "in"
, res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")

op <- options(scipen = 999)
par(xaxs = "i", yaxs = "i", mar = c(4.5, 5, 1, 5.5) + 0.1)

plot(
 r_pred,
 axes = FALSE,
 xlim = c(0, 700e3),
 ylim = c(0, 1300e3),
 xlab = "Easting, GB (km)",
 ylab = "Northing, GB (km)",
 col = rev(heat.colors(50)),
 zlim = range(pred$mean, na.rm = TRUE),
 main = ""
)
```

```
axis(1, at = seq(0, 700e3, by = 100e3), labels = seq(0, 700, by
= 100))
axis(2, at = seq(0, 1300e3, by = 250e3), labels = seq(0, 1300,
by = 250), las = 1)
box()

dev.off()
options(op)

...
```

```
GGplot2 version of predicted intensity
```

This version of the map uses `ggplot2` to visualise predicted fire intensity across the GB. I clipped the prediction raster to the GB boundary to remove values falling outside the land area. I then applied a `log10` colour scale using `viridis` to enhance visibility of lower-intensity areas. This format is much cleaner for presentations and overlays. `coord_sf()` ensures the projection is correctly handled for the EPSG:27700 CRS.

```
```{r ggplot-intensity and mapped, echo=FALSE}
# Ensure gb_sp exists (if not already created earlier)
gb_sp <- as(gb, "Spatial") # 'gb' is Great Britain sf object

# Crop and mask the raster to GB boundary
r_cropped <- raster::crop(r_pred, gb_sp)
r_clipped <- raster::mask(r_cropped, gb_sp)

# Convert to data frame for ggplot
r_df <- as.data.frame(r_clipped, xy = TRUE)
colnames(r_df) <- c("x", "y", "Intensity")
r_df <- r_df[!is.na(r_df$Intensity), ]

# Convert GB boundary to sf for ggplot
gb_sf <- st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# Plot with perceptually uniform viridis scale
ggplot() +
  geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = Intensity))
  +
  scale_fill_viridis_c(trans = "log10") +
  geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
0.3) +
  coord_sf(crs = 27700) +
  labs(
    title = "Predicted fire intensity (LGCP)",
    x = "Easting",
    y = "Northing"
  ) +
  theme_minimal()

...
```

```
## Inspect prediction output

```{r inspect-pred, echo=FALSE}
str(pred)
summary(pred$mean)
```

Notes for the two final - stage rasters

*r_capped      Clipped fire intensity
This raster carries the posterior mean number of fires in each
grid-cell.
When you hand a regular grid (pred_grid) to predict(), INLABru
multiplies the point-wise intensity (fires m ) by
the area of each cell before returning it.
With a 150 150 grid laid over the GB, one cell is roughly 7
km 7 km 5 10 m , so legend values like 40 000
70 000 already refer to fires per cell .
Clipping at the 95-th percentile only flattens the very highest
counts for nicer colours; the units stay the same.

*log_r_clipped  Log clipped fire intensity
Here we take the same land-only raster and apply log1p() ( log
(1 + count) ).
The legend therefore shows log-counts, e.g. a colour bar value
of 12 means
exp(12) 1 1.6 10 expected fires in that cell.
This log stretch is purely for visual contrast; it is not meant
for direct numerical interpretation.

Converting units
* fires m * = r_capped / cell_area
* fires km * _km = r_capped / cell_area 10
(where cell_area = prod(res(r_capped))).

So: r_capped gives raw counts per grid-cell; log_r_clipped is
just the log of those counts for cleaner shading.

```{r ggplot-intensity-heatmap, echo=FALSE}
Calculate cell area in m
cell_area <- prod(res(r_clipped)) # resolution = cell width
height in metres

Convert predicted intensity from per m to per km
r_km2 <- r_clipped / cell_area * 1e6 # 1e6 m = 1 km

Plot the raster
plot(r_km2,
 main = "Clipped Fire Intensity (fires per km)",
 col = rev(heat.colors(50)))

Add GB boundary outline
plot(gb_sp, add = TRUE, border = "black", lwd = 0.8)

```

## Clipped Fire Intensity (fires per km )
```

This map shows the posterior **mean** fire intensity across the GB, **as** estimated **by** the **fitted log**-Gaussian Cox process (LGCP) **model**. To produce this interpretable map:

Predicted intensity was computed using `predict(fit, newdata, formula = ~ exp(field))`, returning an expected number of fires per square metre **for** each prediction cell.

The predictions were rasterised onto a 150 150 regular **grid** covering the GB, with each cell covering approximately 49 km .

The raster was then clipped to GB land using a spatial mask to **remove** sea/background regions.

To improve colour contrast, intensity values were capped at the 95th percentile, reducing the visual **influence** of extreme high predictions without altering the underlying **scale**.

Finally, the raster was unit-converted to fires per km **by** multiplying each cell's predicted value (in fires/m) **by** 1,000,000 and dividing **by** the cell area in m .

The resulting **plot** displays spatial variation in expected fire occurrence, now in fully interpretable units of fires per km , with the **legend** capped **for** readability. This forms the core spatial intensity map before adding environmental covariates in later stages.

```

```{r logtransform plot to ensure readability, echo=FALSE}
Raster -> data frame
r_df <- as.data.frame(r_km2, xy = TRUE)
names(r_df) <- c("x", "y", "fires_km2")
r_df <- r_df[is.finite(r_df$fires_km2),]

Boundary as sf
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

Build plot (no in-plot title; curved lat/long grid; degree
 tick labels)
p <- ggplot() +
 geom_raster(data = r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = fires_km2),
 interpolate = TRUE) +
 geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
 0.4) +
 scale_fill_gradientn(colours = rev(heat.colors(100)), name = "
 Fires per km ",
 breaks = pretty(range(r_df$fires_km2), n
 = 5)) +
 coord_sf(
 crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
 default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
 datum = sf::st_crs(4326),
 xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000), expand = FALSE
) +
 labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +

```

```

theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
theme(
 plot.title = element_blank(),
 panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
 = 0.3),
 panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

print(p) # draw on-screen

Save using the old method (re-render to file)
png("lgcp_predicted_intensity.png", width = 6.5, height = 9,
 units = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

...

Summary of Posterior Fire Intensity (Fires per km)

In addition to the spatial map, we calculate summary statistics
of the posterior mean fire intensity (per km) across the
GB. These values describe how intensity varies over land:

Minimum and maximum: range of predicted fire intensities (note:
max capped at the 95th percentile)

Median and quartiles: show the typical spread across regions

Mean: average predicted intensity over all land grid-cells

Total expected fires: approximate sum over all grid cells

These values provide context for interpreting the map, revealing
whether high fire risks are concentrated in just a few
locations or spread across larger areas.
````{r Summary of latent field, echo=FALSE}
# Summarise values from the raster (fires per km )
intensity_summary <- summary(values(r_km2))
total_expected_fires <- sum(values(r_km2), na.rm = TRUE)

# Format and display table
kable(
  data.frame(
    Statistic = c(
      "Minimum", "1st_Quartile", "Median", "Mean",
      "3rd_Quartile", "Maximum", "Missing(masked)",
      "Total_expected_fires(sum_over_land)"
    ),
    Value = c(
      round(intensity_summary["Min."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["1st_Qu."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Median"], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Mean"], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["3rd_Qu."], 2),
      round(intensity_summary["Max."], 2),
      intensity_summary["NA's"],
      round(total_expected_fires, 1)
    )
  )
)

```

```

    )
  ),
  caption = "Posterior mean fire intensity (fires per km )
            across Great Britain"
)
...

## Load and Merge Land Cover Data
We use the 2023 GB Land Cover Map (LCM) provided as 1 km
dominant aggregate raster layers for both Great Britain and
Northern Ireland. These datasets classify each 1 km grid
cell into a single dominant land cover type.

Notes
CRS Handling: The GB raster uses the British National Grid (EPSG
:27700) while the NI raster uses the Irish Grid (EPSG:29903)
. We reproject NI to ensure a consistent spatial reference.

Mosaicking: After reprojection, the terra::mosaic() function
combines the rasters into a seamless GB-wide layer.

Resolution: Both rasters have a 1 km 1 km resolution, meaning
each cell represents 1 km .

This merged raster (LC_all) will now serve as our covariate
layer for incorporating land cover into the spatial model.

```{r step1-load-lc, echo=FALSE}
Load the GB land cover raster (1km aggregated classes)
LC_path <- "C:/Users/Bear/Desktop/Dissertation/DL_FIRE_M-C61_
628685/data.landcover.2023/lcm-2023-1km_6023459/aggregate_
class/gb2023lcm1km_dominant_aggregate.tif"
LC_dom <- terra::rast(LC_path)

Check projection (should be EPSG:27700)
terra::crs(LC_dom)
...

Visualise Merged Land Cover Raster
To confirm that the land cover rasters for Great Britain and
Northern Ireland have been correctly loaded, reprojected,
and mosaicked, we visualise the merged raster below.

Notes
This plot shows the dominant land cover class in each 1 km
cell across the GB.

Colour categories correspond to integer class codes in the
raster, which refer to aggregated land cover types (e.g.,
arable, forest, urban).

A legend with class labels can be added later using a look-up
table (LUT) if desired.

```

```

Let me know if you'd like the class legend added or want to
 overlay it on a GB boundary.
```{r landcover_plot, echo=FALSE}
library(terra)
library(viridis)

# Basic plot of the GB-only land cover raster
plot(LC_dom,
      main="2023 Dominant Land Cover (1 km , Great Britain only)",
      col=viridis(10),
      axes=TRUE,
      legend=FALSE)
```

```{r plot-aggregated-landcover, echo=FALSE, message=FALSE}
library(terra)
library(ggplot2)

# Define the mapping from 1-10 aggregated classes (AC
  Identifiers)
agg_classes<-c(
  "1"="Broadleaf woodland",
  "2"="Coniferous woodland",
  "3"="Arable",
  "4"="Improved grassland",
  "5"="Semi-natural grassland",
  "6"="Mountain, heath and bog",
  "7"="Saltwater",
  "8"="Freshwater",
  "9"="Coastal",
  "10"="Built-up areas and gardens"
)

# Convert merged raster to dataframe for ggplot
lc_df<-as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy=TRUE, na.rm=TRUE)
names(lc_df)[3]<-"code"

# Filter only values in 1:10 (aggregated classes)
lc_df<-lc_df[lc_df$code%in%1:10,]

# Assign labels
lc_df$label<-factor(agg_classes[as.character(lc_df$code)],
  levels=agg_classes)

# Plot
ggplot(lc_df, aes(x=x, y=y, fill=label)) +
  geom_raster() +
  coord_equal() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(name="Land cover (aggregated)", option
    ="D") +
  labs(
    title="2023 Dominant Land Cover (1 km )",
    subtitle="UKCEH 10-class aggregated land cover (Great
      Britain+Northern Ireland)"
  ) +

```

```

%%theme_minimal()
%%theme(legend.position="right")
```

```{r|plot-landcover-aggregated,echo=FALSE,message=FALSE,
  warning=FALSE}
#Landcovermap:sameaxes/styleaslastfigure,unotitle,
  stacked(single-column)legendwithsensiblecolours

library(ggplot2)
library(sf)
library(terra)
library(grid)

#Aggregatedclasslabels
agg_lookup<-uc(
  "1"="Broadleafwoodland",
  "2"="Coniferouswoodland",
  "3"="Arable",
  "4"="Improvedgrassland",
  "5"="Semi-naturalgrassland",
  "6"="Mountain,heathandbog",
  "7"="Saltwater",
  "8"="Freshwater",
  "9"="Coastal",
  "10"="Built-upareasandgardens"
)

#Raster->dataframe(BNGcoords)
lc_df<-as.data.frame(LC_dom,xy=TRUE,na.rm=TRUE)
names(lc_df)[3]<-"code"
lc_df<-lc_df[lc_df$code%in%1:10,]
lc_df$label<-factor(agg_lookup[as.character(lc_df$code)],
  levels=agg_lookup)

#Boundaryas_sf
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

#Colourpaletteonly:brighterbroadleafgreen;mediumbrown
  arable;softeryellow/orangegrasslands;deeperpurpleheath
  /bog;darkergreybuilt-up
col_map<-uc(
  "Broadleafwoodland"===== "#2ECC71",#brightergreen
  "Coniferouswoodland"===== "#006400",#darkgreen
  "Arable"===== "#B77E43",#mediumbrown/ochre
  "Improvedgrassland"===== "#F1D54E",#calmyellow
  "Semi-naturalgrassland"===== "#F39C12",#softerorange
  "Mountain,heathandbog"===== "#7A4E9C",#deeperpurple
  "Saltwater"===== "#1F78B4",#blue
  "Freshwater"===== "#A6CEE3",#lightblue
  "Coastal"===== "#F4C27A",#sand
  "Built-upareasandgardens"=" "#6E6E6E"##darkergrey
)

#Buildplot(BNGdraw;curvedlat/longgrid;degree ticklabels
)
p<-ggplot()+

```

```

geom_raster(data=lc_df, aes(x=x, y=y, fill=label)) +
geom_sf(data=gb_sf, fill=NA, color="black", linewidth=0.4) +
scale_fill_manual(values=col_map, name="Land cover (aggregated)", drop=FALSE) +
coord_sf(
  crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
  default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
  datum=sf::st_crs(4326),
  xlim=c(0, 700000), ylim=c(0, 1300000), expand=FALSE
) +
labs(x="Easting", y="Northing") +
theme_bw(base_size=11) +
theme(
  plot.title=element_blank(),
  panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80", linewidth=0.3),
  panel.grid.minor=element_blank(),
  legend.position="right",
  legend.title=element_text(size=10),
  legend.text=element_text(size=9),
  legend.key.height=grid::unit(0.45, "cm")
) +
guides(fill=guide_legend(ncol=1, byrow=FALSE, title.position="top", title.hjust=0))

print(p)

ggsave("landcover2023_map.pdf", width=6.5, height=9, units="in", dpi=300)

...

```{r creat-frims_df_lc, echo=FALSE}
library(terra)
library(sp)

Make a copy of fire points data
frims_df_lc <- frims_df

Extract raster land cover codes at fire locations
extracted <- terra::extract(LC_dom, vect(frims_df_lc))

Check if any NA values (meaning points outside raster extent)
if (any(is.na(extracted[,2]))) {
 warning("Some fire points fall outside the land cover raster extent!")
}

Define land cover class lookup (integer codes to labels)
agg_lookup <- c(
 "1" = "Broadleaf woodland",
 "2" = "Coniferous woodland",
 "3" = "Arable",
 "4" = "Improved grassland",
 "5" = "Semi-natural grassland",

```

```

 "6" = "Mountain, heath and bog",
 "7" = "Saltwater",
 "8" = "Freshwater",
 "9" = "Coastal",
 "10" = "Built-up areas and gardens"
)

Add landcover as a factor column to firms_df_lc
firms_df_lc$landcover <- factor(agg_lookup[as.character(
 extracted[,2])],
 levels = agg_lookup)

Check new column
table(firms_df_lc$landcover, useNA = "ifany")

...

```{r fit-lgcp-landcover-fixed, message=FALSE, warning=FALSE}

# 1. Set the reference level to something that exists in fire
data
firms_df_lc$landcover <- relevel(firms_df_lc$landcover, ref = "
Arable")

# 2. Explicitly add a 'coordinates' column to the data (INLABru
needs this!)
firms_df_lc@data$coordinates <- coordinates(firms_df_lc)

# 3. Define component formula
cmp_lc <- ~
landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
  hyper = list(prec = list(prior = "pc.prec", param =
c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
field(coordinates, model = spde)

# 4. Fit the LGCP model with land cover as a covariate
fit_lc <- lgcp(
  components = cmp_lc,
  data = firms_df_lc,
  domain = list(coordinates = mesh)
)

# 5. Extract and format summary of land cover effects
lc_tab <- as.data.frame(fit_lc$summary.random$landcover)
num_cols <- sapply(lc_tab, is.numeric)
lc_tab[, num_cols] <- lapply(lc_tab[, num_cols], round, 3)

# 6. Display the results as a table
knitr::kable(
  lc_tab,
  caption = "LGCP land-cover effects (relative to Arable)"
)

...

```

```

`{r_predict-intensity-lc-firemap, message=FALSE, warning=FALSE
}
# End-to-end: compute land-cover-only prediction raster ->
  ggplot map
# (same axes/style as previous maps, no title, legend "Fires per
  km  "),
# and save using png()+print()+dev.off() to lc_only_prediction.
  png

# 1) Lookup for aggregated land-cover labels (levels must match
  model)
agg_lookup<-c(
  "1"="Broadleaf woodland", "2"="Coniferous woodland", "3"="Arable
  ", "4"="Improved grassland",
  "5"="Semi-natural grassland", "6"="Mountain, heath and bog
  ", "7"="Saltwater", "8"="Freshwater",
  "9"="Coastal", "10"="Built-up areas and gardens"
)

# 2) Build prediction grid from LC_dom and map to model factor
  levels
grid_df<-as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy=TRUE, na.rm=FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3]<-"code"
grid_df$landcover<-factor(agg_lookup[as.character(grid_df$code
)],
  levels=levels(firms_df_lc$
  landcover))
grid_df<-grid_df[!is.na(grid_df$landcover),]

# 3) Predict land-cover-only effect with fitted model
grid_spdf<-SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  coords=grid_df[,c("x", "y")],
  data=data.frame(landcover=grid_df$landcover),
  proj4string=CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)
lp_lc<-predict(fit_lc, newdata=grid_spdf, formula=~
  landcover, n.samples=100)

# 4) Write predictions back to a raster and exponentiate to
  intensity
logint_lc<-rast(LC_dom); values(logint_lc)<-NA_real_
cells<-cellFromXY(logint_lc, grid_df[,c("x", "y")])
values(logint_lc)[cells]<-lp_lc$mean
names(logint_lc)<-"log_intensity"

r_df<-as.data.frame(logint_lc, xy=TRUE, na.rm=TRUE)
r_df$intensity<-exp(r_df$log_intensity)

# 5) Boundary (sp->sf) for outline
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

# 6) Plot (BNG draw with curved lat/long grid + degree ticks; no
  in-plot title)
p<-ggplot()+

```

```

geom_raster(data=r_df, aes(x=ux, y=uy, fill=intensity)) +
  geom_sf(data=gb_sf, fill=NA, color="black", linewidth=0.4) +
  scale_fill_gradientn(
    colours=c("white", "yellow", "orange", "red"),
    name="Relative intensity (land cover only)",
    na.value="grey90"
  ) +
  coord_sf(
    crs=sf::st_crs(27700), default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum=sf::st_crs(4326), xlim=c(0, 700000), ylim=c(0, 1300000),
    expand=FALSE
  ) +
  labs(x="Easting", y="Northing") +
  theme_bw(base_size=11) +
  theme(
    plot.title=element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80", linewidth=0.3),
    panel.grid.minor=element_blank()
  )

#7) Save using the reliable method
print(p)
png("lc_only_prediction.png", width=6.5, height=9, units="in",
    res=300, type="cairo", bg="white")
print(p)
dev.off()

...

```{r save-lc-map, echo=FALSE}
Land-cover-only prediction as **fires per km** (includes intercept), styled like previous maps,
and saved reliably via png() + print(p) + dev.off().

#1) Aggregated land-cover lookup (ensure levels match the model)
agg_lookup<-c(
 "1"="Broadleaf woodland", "2"="Coniferous woodland", "3"="Arable",
 "4"="Improved grassland",
 "5"="Semi-natural grassland", "6"="Mountain, heath and bog",
 "7"="Saltwater", "8"="Freshwater",
 "9"="Coastal", "10"="Built-up areas and gardens"
)

#2) Prediction grid from land-cover raster (BNG coords)
grid_df<-as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy=TRUE, na.rm=FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3]<- "code"
grid_df$landcover<-factor(agg_lookup[as.character(grid_df$code)])

```

```

#####levels=levels(firms_df_lc$
 landcover))
grid_df<-grid_df[!is.na(grid_df$landcover),]

grid_spdf<-SpatialPointsDataFrame(
 coords=grid_df[,c("x","y")],
 data=data.frame(landcover=grid_df$landcover),
 proj4string=CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)

#3) Predict land-cover effect; convert to intensity per km^2
lp_lc<-predict(fit_lc,newdata=grid_spdf,formula=~
 landcover, n.samples=100)

Intercept mean (fallback for naming)
int_name<-if("Intercept"%in%rownames(fit_lc$summary.fixed
))"Intercept"else"Intercept"
beta0<-fit_lc$summary.fixed[int_name,"mean"]

eta_mean<-lp_lc$mean+beta0#####linear
 predictor including intercept
lambda_km2<-exp(eta_mean)*1e6#####intensity per
 km^2 (LGCP is per m^2 1e6)

#4) Rasterise predictions
int_r<-rast(LC_dom);values(int_r)<-NA_real_
cells<-cellFromXY(int_r,grid_df[,c("x","y")])
values(int_r)[cells]<-lambda_km2
names(int_r)<-"fires_km2"

#5) Data frame for ggplot + GB boundary as sf
r_df_km2<-as.data.frame(int_r,xy=TRUE,na.rm=TRUE)
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

#6) Plot (BNG draw with curved lat/long grid + degree ticks; no
 in-plot title)
p<-ggplot()+
 geom_raster(data=r_df_km2,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=fires_
 km2))+
 geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=
 0.4)+
 scale_fill_gradientn(
 colours=c("white","yellow","orange","red"),
 name="Fires per km ",
 na.value="grey90"
)+
 coord_sf(
 crs=sf::st_crs(27700),default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
 datum=sf::st_crs(4326),xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(0,
 1300000),
 expand=FALSE
)+
 labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
 theme_bw(base_size=11)+
 theme(
 plot.title=element_blank(),

```

```

panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
 = 0.3),
panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

#7) Save reliably
print(p)
png("lc_only_prediction_km2.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units
 = "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

...

Extend the land cover covariate and prediction map
```{r GB-map-with-lc-and-SPDE, message=FALSE}

# Assuming:
# - firms_df_lc has coordinates, landcover factor column, and is
  projected
# - mesh and spde are already defined

#1. Define model components with landcover covariate + spatial
  field
cmp_full <- coordinates ~
landcover(main = landcover, model = "factor_contrast",
          hyper = list(prec = list(prior = "pc.prec", param =
            c(0.5, 0.01)))) +
field(coordinates, model = spde)

#2. Fit LGCP model
fit_full <- lgcpc(
  components = cmp_full,
  data = firms_df_lc,
  domain = list(coordinates = mesh)
)

#3. Create prediction grid (from LC raster)
grid_df <- as.data.frame(LC_dom, xy = TRUE, na.rm = FALSE)
names(grid_df)[3] <- "landcover"
# Define the mapping: raw raster values to land cover labels
lc_mapping <- c(
  "1" = "Broadleaved woodland",
  "2" = "Coniferous woodland",
  "3" = "Arable",
  "4" = "Improved grassland",
  "5" = "Semi-natural grassland",
  "6" = "Mountain, heath and bog",

```

```

uu"7" uu="Saltwater",
uu"8" uu="Freshwater",
uu"9" uu="Coastal",
uu"10" uu="Built-up areas and gardens"
)

# Convert raster values to factor levels used in the model
grid_df$landcover <- factor(
  uu lc_mapping[as.character(grid_df$landcover)],
  uu levels = levels(firms_df_lc$landcover)
)

grid_df$x <- as.numeric(grid_df$x)
grid_df$y <- as.numeric(grid_df$y)

grid_spdf <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  uu coords = grid_df[,c("x", "y")],
  uu data = data.frame(landcover = grid_df$landcover),
  uu proj4string = CRS("+init=epsg:27700")
)

# 4. Predict log-intensity including spatial field + covariate
lp_full <- predict(
  uu fit_full,
  uu newdata = grid_spdf,
  uu formula = ~landcover + field,
  uu n.samples = 100
)

# 5. Convert prediction to raster
logint_full_raster <- setValues(rast(LC_dom), lp_full$mean)

# 6. Plot with heat color scale
r_df <- as.data.frame(logint_full_raster, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
colnames(r_df)[3] <- "log_intensity"

ggplot(r_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = log_intensity)) +
  uu geom_raster() +
  uu scale_fill_gradientn(
  uuuu colours = rev(RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(9, "YlOrRd")),
  uuuu name = "Log-Intensity"
  uu) +
  uu coord_equal() +
  uu labs(title = "Predicted Log-Intensity (Land Cover + Spatial Field)",
  uuuuuu x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
  uu theme_minimal()
```



```

```{r raw-combined, echo=FALSE}
PLOT-ONLY (no refit / no re-predict): rework the visual of
 existing_r_df(x, y, log_intensity)
to match prior maps (curved lat/long grid, degree tick labels,
 no_in-plot_title),

```


```

```

#_and_save_with_the_reliable_png()+_print(p)+_dev.off()_method
.

library(ggplot2)
library(sf)

p<-_ggplot()+
  _geom_raster(data=_r_df, _aes(x=_x, _y=_y, _fill=_log_
    intensity))+
  _scale_fill_gradientn(
    _colours=_rev(RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(9, "YlOrRd")),
    _name=_ "Log-intensity"
  )+
  _coord_sf(
    _crs=_sf::st_crs(27700),
    _default_crs=_sf::st_crs(27700),
    _datum=_sf::st_crs(4326), _#_curved_lat/long_
      _graticule+_degree_tick_labels
    _xlim=_c(0, 700000), _ylim=_c(0, 1300000),
    _expand=_FALSE
  )+
  _labs(x=_ "Easting", _y=_ "Northing")+
  _theme_bw(base_size=_11)+
  _theme(
    _plot.title=_element_blank(),
    _panel.grid.major=_element_line(colour=_ "grey80", _linewidth
      _=0.3),
    _panel.grid.minor=_element_blank()
  )

print(p)
png("lgcp_full_logintensity.png", _width=_6.5, _height=_9, _units
  _="in", _res=_300, _type=_ "cairo", _bg=_ "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

...

```{r_summary-combine-model, _echo=FALSE}
#_Extract_raw_predicted_log-intensity_values
log_pred<-_lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]

#_Summary_of_log-intensity
log_summary<-_summary(log_pred)

#_Exponentiate_to_get_predicted_intensity_(fires_per_km, _since
 _raster_is_1km_resolution)
intensity<-_exp(log_pred)

#_Summary_of_intensity_(linear_scale)
intensity_summary<-_summary(intensity)

#_95th_percentile_of_predicted_intensity
intensity_95th<-_quantile(intensity, _0.95, _na.rm=_TRUE)

```

```

Total expected number of fires across GB (sum of expected
 fires per cell)
total_expected_fires <- sum(intensity, na.rm=TRUE)

Display all summaries
cat(" Summary of predicted log-intensity (raw):\n")
print(log_summary)

cat("\n Summary of predicted intensity (fires per km):\n")
print(intensity_summary)

cat("\n 95th percentile of predicted intensity:\n")
print(intensity_95th)

cat("\n Total expected fires across GB:\n")
print(round(total_expected_fires, 2))

...

```{r full-quantile-summary, echo=FALSE}
# Remove NA values
log_pred <- lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]

# Generate quantiles from 0% to 100% in 1% steps
log_quantiles <- quantile(log_pred, probs=seq(0, 1, by=0.01)
)

# Print nicely
print(round(log_quantiles, 2))
# Zoom in on upper 90-100 % quantiles
tail_quantiles <- quantile(log_pred, probs=seq(0.90, 1, by=
0.01))
print(round(tail_quantiles, 2))

...

```{r hit-log-intensity-full, echo=FALSE}
Filter for zoom range: log-intensity between 0 and 20
log_pred_zoom <- log_pred[log_pred > 0 & log_pred <= 20]

Plot refined histogram
hist(
 log_pred_zoom,
 breaks=100,
 main="",
 xlab="Log-Intensity",
 col="tomato",
 border="white"
)

Add reference lines
abline(v=quantile(log_pred, c(0.60, 0.70, 0.80)), col=c("
blue", "green", "purple"), lty=2)

```

```

legend("topright", legend=c("60%", "70%", "80%"),
 col=c("blue", "green", "purple"), lty=2, bty="n")
```

```{r save-log-hist, echo=FALSE}

Save the zoomed-in log-intensity histogram
png("log_intensity_histogram_trimmed.png", width=800, height=600,
 res=120)

Plot histogram
hist(log_pred[log_pred>0 & log_pred<=20],
 breaks=100,
 main="",
 xlab="Log-Intensity",
 col="tomato",
 border="white")

Add quantile reference lines
abline(v=quantile(log_pred, c(0.60, 0.70, 0.80)), col=c("
 blue", "green", "purple"), lty=2)
legend("topright", legend=c("60%", "70%", "80%"),
 col=c("blue", "green", "purple"), lty=2, bty="n")

dev.off()
```

```{r final-summary-table, echo=FALSE}

1. Get raw predicted values
log_pred<-lp_full$mean[!is.na(lp_full$mean)]
intensity<-exp(log_pred)

2. Create summary table
summary_table<-data.frame(
 Scale=c("Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "
 Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity", "Log-Intensity",
 "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity",
 "Intensity", "Intensity", "Intensity"),
 Statistic=c("Min", "1st Quartile", "Median", "Mean", "3rd
 Quartile", "Max",
 "Min", "1st Quartile", "Median", "Mean", "3rd
 Quartile", "Max", "Total Fires"),
 Value=c(
 round(min(log_pred), 2),
 round(quantile(log_pred, 0.25), 2),
 round(median(log_pred), 2),
 round(mean(log_pred), 2),
 round(quantile(log_pred, 0.75), 2),
 round(max(log_pred), 2),

 round(min(intensity), 2),
 round(quantile(intensity, 0.25), 2),

```

```

round(median(intensity), 2),
mean(intensity), ##likely to be Inf
round(quantile(intensity, 0.75), 2),
max(intensity), ##likely to be Inf
sum(intensity, na.rm=TRUE) ##total predicted fires
)

#Display in console
print(summary_table)

...

```{r clipped-anc-scaling-combined-field, echo=FALSE}
#Step1: Extract prediction values
log_pred_full <- lp_full$mean
log_pred_full <- log_pred_full[!is.na(log_pred_full)] ##remove NA for quantile

#Step2: Compute 80th percentile on log scale
log_cap_full <- quantile(log_pred_full, 0.70)

#Step3: Clamp log prediction vector
log_pred_clipped_full <- pmin(lp_full$mean, log_cap_full)

#Step4: Exponentiate to get intensity
intensity_clipped_full <- exp(log_pred_clipped_full)

#Step5: Create raster (fires per km )
r_raster_full <- setValues(rast(LC_dom), intensity_clipped_full)

#Step6: Mask to GB using raster package for compatibility
r_raster_r_full <- raster::raster(r_raster_full) ##convert to raster format
r_cropped_full <- raster::crop(r_raster_r_full, gb_sp)
r_masked_full <- raster::mask(r_cropped_full, gb_sp)

#Step7: Already in km , no need to rescale
r_km2_full <- terra::rast(r_masked_full) ##convert back to terra if needed

#Step8: Plot
plot(r_km2_full,
      main=paste0("Fire Intensity (70th percentile clipped at ",
                  round(exp(log_cap_full), 1), " fires/km )"),
      col=rev(heat.colors(50)),
      zlim=c(0, round(exp(log_cap_full), 1)))
plot(gb_sp, add=TRUE, border="black", lwd=0.8)

...

```{r save-fina-output-full-model, echo=FALSE}

```

```

80th percentile clipped intensity map (land cover + field),
 styled like previous maps:
no in-plot title
BNG draw with curved lat/long graticule and degree tick
 labels
legend "Fires per km "
save via png() + print(p) + dev.off() to lgcp_fullmap_
 capped80.png

library(sf)
library(ggplot2)

Raster -> data frame for ggplot
r_df_full <- as.data.frame(r_km2_full, xy = TRUE, na.rm = TRUE)
names(r_df_full)[3] <- "fires_km2"

GB outline as sf
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

Upper limit from clip (on natural scale)
cap_val <- exp(log_cap_full)

p <- ggplot() +
 geom_raster(data = r_df_full, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = fires_
 km2)) +
 geom_sf(data = gb_sf, fill = NA, color = "black", linewidth =
 0.4) +
 scale_fill_gradientn(
 colours = rev(heat.colors(50)),
 name = "Fires per km ",
 limits = c(0, cap_val),
 oob = scales::squish
) +
 coord_sf(
 crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
 default_crs = sf::st_crs(27700),
 datum = sf::st_crs(4326), ##### # curved lat/long grid
 + degree tick labels
 xlim = c(0, 700000), ylim = c(0, 1300000),
 expand = FALSE
) +
 labs(x = "Easting", y = "Northing") +
 theme_bw(base_size = 11) +
 theme(
 plot.title = element_blank(),
 panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey80", linewidth
 = 0.3),
 panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)

print(p)
png("lgcp_fullmap_capped80.png", width = 6.5, height = 9, units =
 "in", res = 300, type = "cairo", bg = "white")
print(p)
dev.off()

...

```

```

```{r Summary of clipped intensity, echo=FALSE}
# Extract values from the *full model* raster (fires per km2, 1
  km2 resolution)
vals_full <- as.numeric(values(r_km2_full))

# Get summary stats
summary_km2_full <- summary(vals_full)
total_expected_fires_full <- sum(vals_full, na.rm=TRUE)

# Format and display table
kable(
  data.frame(
    Statistic=c(
      "Minimum", "1st Quartile", "Median", "Mean",
      "3rd Quartile", "Maximum (clipped)", "Missing (NA)",
      "Total expected fires (over land)"
    ),
    Value=c(
      round(summary_km2_full["Min."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["1st Qu."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Median"], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Mean"], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["3rd Qu."], 2),
      round(summary_km2_full["Max."], 2),
      summary_km2_full["NA's"],
      round(total_expected_fires_full, 1)
    )
  ),
  caption="Posterior mean fire intensity (fires per km2)
  across Great Britain from the full LGCP model (clipped at 70
  th percentile)"
)

...

```{r model_1_uncert, echo=FALSE}
same model, just add samples to get sd & CIs
pred <- predict(fit, pred_grid, ~exp(field), n.samples=1000)

you'll have:
pred$mean, pred$sd, pred$q0.025, pred$q0.975
pred$cv <- pred$sd / pmax(pred$mean, 1e-12) # optional:
 relative uncertainty

...

```{r model_1_uncert_map, echo=FALSE}
# Build a raster of CV from the prediction grid + pred$cv
library(raster)
library(sp)
library(ggplot2)
library(sf)

# 1) Build CV raster from predictions
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)

```

```

cv_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1],y=coords[,2],cv=pred$
  cv)
r_cv<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(cv_xyz)
raster::crs(r_cv)<-raster::crs(pred_grid)

#2) Reproject boundary to match raster CRS and mask
gb_sp_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp,raster::crs(r_cv))
r_cv_land<-raster::mask(raster::crop(r_cv,gb_sp_bng),gb_sp_
  bng)

#3) Raster->data frame (same workflow as mean map)
r_df_cv<-as.data.frame(r_cv_land,xy=TRUE)
names(r_df_cv)<-c("x","y","cv")
r_df_cv<-r_df_cv[is.finite(r_df_cv$cv),]

#4) Plot and save using existing style
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_cv<-ggplot()+
  geom_raster(data=r_df_cv,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=cv),
    interpolate=TRUE)+
  geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=
    0.4)+
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),name="
    CV (sd/mean)",
    breaks=pretty(range(r_df_cv$cv),n=5)
  )+
  coord_sf(
    crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum=sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE
  )+
  labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
  theme_bw(base_size=11)+
  theme(
    plot.title=element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80",linewidth
      =0.3),
    panel.grid.minor=element_blank()
  )

print(p_cv)

png("lgcp_relative_uncertainty_cv_land.png",width=6.5,height
  =9,
  units="in",res=300,type="cairo",bg="white")
print(p_cv)
dev.off()

...

```{r model_1_uncert_table,echo=FALSE}
#Land mask (TRUE on land, FALSE at sea; no NAs)
gb_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp,sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid
)))

```

```

ov<-sp::over(pred_grid,gb_bng)#data.frameof
 polygonattributes
land_idx<-!is.na(ov[[1]])#logicalvector

#Land-onlyCV
cv<-pred$cv
keep<-land_idx&!is.finite(cv)

cv_stats<-data.frame(
 Statistic=c("Min","Q1","Median","Mean","Q3","Max","P90","P99",
 "Share CV<0.5","Share CV<1.0","N (land)","NAs (land)"),
 Value=c(
 min(cv[keep],na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(cv[keep],0.25,na.rm=TRUE),
 median(cv[keep],na.rm=TRUE),
 mean(cv[keep],na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(cv[keep],0.75,na.rm=TRUE),
 max(cv[keep],na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(cv[keep],0.90,na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(cv[keep],0.99,na.rm=TRUE),
 mean(cv[keep]<0.5,na.rm=TRUE),
 mean(cv[keep]<1.0,na.rm=TRUE),
 sum(keep,na.rm=TRUE),
 sum(land_idx&!is.finite(cv),na.rm=TRUE)
)
)

cv_stats$Value<-round(cv_stats$Value,3)

knitr::kable(cv_stats,
 align=c("l","r"),
 caption="Model 1 Relative uncertainty (CV =
 sd/mean) over land pixels")

write.csv(cv_stats,"m1_cv_summary.csv",row.names=FALSE)

#Hyperparameters table unchanged
knitr::kable(fit$summary.hyperpar,digits=3,
 caption="Model 1 SPDE hyperparameters")

...

```{rmodel_1_uncert_CI_MAP,echo=FALSE}
library(raster)
library(sp)
library(sf)
library(ggplot2)

#1)95%CIwidthateachgridpoint
width95<-pred$q0.975-pred$q0.025

#2)Makearasterfrompredictiongrid+width
coords<-sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
w_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1],y=coords[,2],width95=width95)

```

```

r_w<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz)
raster::crs(r_w)<-raster::crs(pred_grid)

#3) Mask to land
gb_sp_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp,raster::crs(r_w))
r_w_land<-raster::mask(raster::crop(r_w,gb_sp_bng),gb_sp_bng)

#4) Raster to data frame
r_df_w<-as.data.frame(r_w_land,xy=TRUE)
names(r_df_w)<-c("x","y","width95")
r_df_w<-r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95),]

#5) Plot (same style as mean map)
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w<-ggplot()+
  geom_raster(data=r_df_w,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=width95),
    interpolate=TRUE)+
  geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=0.4)+
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),
    name="95% CI width",
    breaks=pretty(range(r_df_w$width95),n=5))+
  coord_sf(
    crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum=sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE
  )+
  labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
  theme_bw(base_size=11)+
  theme(
    plot.title=element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80",linewidth=0.3),
    panel.grid.minor=element_blank()
  )

print(p_w)

#6) Save (same method)
png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m1.png",width=6.5,height=9,units="in",
  "in",
  res=300,type="cairo",bg="white")
print(p_w)
dev.off()

...

```{r model_1_uncert_CI_table,echo=FALSE}
w<-r_df_w$width95#land-only values from masked raster ->df
w_stats<-data.frame(
 Statistic=c("Min","Q1","Median","Mean","Q3","Max","P90","P99"),

```

```

w_Value = round(c(min(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.25, na.rm=TRUE),
 median(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 mean(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.75, na.rm=TRUE),
 max(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.90, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.99, na.rm=TRUE)), 3)
)
knitr::kable(w_stats, align=c("l", "r"),
 caption="Model 1 95% CI width (fires km-2)
 over land pixels")
...

```{r model_2_uncert, echo=FALSE}
#---insert these lines just before predicting with fit_lc---

#Give pred_grid a data slot and add the 'coordinates' column
  expected by field(coordinates, ...)
pred_grid <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(
  pred_grid,
  data = data.frame(coordinates = sp::coordinates(pred_grid))
)

#Add land-cover factor at grid points with the SAME levels as
  in training
lc_codes <- terra::extract(LC_dom, terra::vect(pred_grid))[, 2]
  #integers 1..10
pred_grid$landcover <- factor(
  agg_lookup[as.character(lc_codes)],
  levels = levels(firms_df_lc$landcover) #keeps "Arable" as
  reference
)

#Land-cover only predictions + uncertainty
pred_lc <- predict(fit_lc, pred_grid, ~exp(landcover), n.
  samples = 1000)
pred_lc$cv <- pred_lc$sd / pmax(pred_lc$mean, 1e-12)
pred_lc$width95 <- pred_lc$q0.975 - pred_lc$q0.025

...

```{r model_2_uncert_map, echo=FALSE}
library(raster)
library(sp)
library(sf)
library(ggplot2)

#Build a raster of CV from pred_lc at pred_grid coords
coords <- sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
cv_xyz <- data.frame(x = coords[, 1], y = coords[, 2], cv = pred_
 lc$cv)

r_cv <- raster::rasterFromXYZ(cv_xyz)

```

```

raster::crs(r_cv) <- raster::crs(pred_grid)

Mask to GB land
gb_sp_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, raster::crs(r_cv))
r_cv_land <- raster::mask(raster::crop(r_cv, gb_sp_bng), gb_sp_bng)

Raster to dataframe
r_df_cv <- as.data.frame(r_cv_land, xy=TRUE)
names(r_df_cv) <- c("x", "y", "cv")
r_df_cv <- r_df_cv[is.finite(r_df_cv$cv),]

Plot (same style as mean map)
gb_sf <- sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_cv <- ggplot() +
 geom_raster(data=r_df_cv, aes(x=x, y=y, fill=cv),
 interpolate=TRUE) +
 geom_sf(data=gb_sf, fill=NA, color="black", linewidth=0.4) +
 scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),
 name="CV (sd/mean)",
 breaks=pretty(range(r_df_cv$cv), n=5)) +
 coord_sf(
 crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
 default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
 datum=sf::st_crs(4326),
 xlim=c(0, 700000), ylim=c(0, 1300000), expand=FALSE) +
 labs(x="Easting", y="Northing") +
 theme_bw(base_size=11) +
 theme(
 plot.title=element_blank(),
 panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80", linewidth=0.3),
 panel.grid.minor=element_blank())

print(p_cv)

Save
png("lgcp_relative_uncertainty_cv_m2.png", width=6.5, height=9,
 units="in",
 res=300, type="cairo", bg="white")
print(p_cv)
dev.off()

...

```{r model_2_uncert_table, echo=FALSE}
# Land mask using GB boundary and prediction points (BNG)
gb_bng <- sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid)))
ov <- sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng) # polygon overlay
land_idx <- !is.na(ov[, 1]) # TRUE on land

```

```

# Land-only CV vector
cv_<-pred_lc$cv
cv_land<-cv[land_idx&is.finite(cv)]

# Summary table (land only)
cv_stats_lc<-data.frame(
  Statistic=c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
    "Share CV<0.5", "Share CV<1.0", "N (land)", "NAs (land)"),
  Value=c(
    min(cv_land, na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(cv_land, 0.25, na.rm=TRUE),
    median(cv_land, na.rm=TRUE),
    mean(cv_land, na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(cv_land, 0.75, na.rm=TRUE),
    max(cv_land, na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(cv_land, 0.90, na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(cv_land, 0.99, na.rm=TRUE),
    mean(cv_land<0.5, na.rm=TRUE),
    mean(cv_land<1.0, na.rm=TRUE),
    length(cv_land),
    sum(land_idx&!is.finite(cv), na.rm=TRUE)
  )
)

cv_stats_lc$Value<-round(cv_stats_lc$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(cv_stats_lc,
  align=c("l", "r"),
  caption="Model 2 (land-cover only) Relative
  uncertainty (CV = sd/mean) over land pixels")

# Hyperparameters table
knitr::kable(fit_lc$summary.hyperpar, digits=3,
  caption="Model 2 (land-cover only)
  Hyperparameters")

```
```{r model_2_uncert_CI_MAP, echo=FALSE}
library(raster)
library(sp)
library(sf)
library(ggplot2)

# 1) 95% CI width at each grid point
width95<-pred_lc$q0.975-pred_lc$q0.025

# 2) Make a raster from prediction grid + width
coords<-sp::coordinates(pred_grid)
w_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1], y=coords[,2], width95=width95)
r_w<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz)
raster::crs(r_w)<-raster::crs(pred_grid)

```

```

#_3)_Mask_to_land
gb_sp_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp,raster::crs(r_w))
r_w_land<-raster::mask(raster::crop(r_w,gb_sp_bng),gb_sp_bng)

#_4)_Raster_to_dataframe
r_df_w<-as.data.frame(r_w_land,xy=TRUE)
names(r_df_w)<-c("x","y","width95")
r_df_w<-r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95),]

#_5)_Plot
gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w<-ggplot()+
  geom_raster(data=r_df_w,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=width95),
    interpolate=TRUE)+
  geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=0.4)+
  scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),
    name="95% CI width",
    breaks=pretty(range(r_df_w$width95),n=5))+
  coord_sf(
    crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
    datum=sf::st_crs(4326),
    xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE
  )+
  labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
  theme_bw(base_size=11)+
  theme(
    plot.title=element_blank(),
    panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey80",linewidth=0.3),
    panel.grid.minor=element_blank()
  )

print(p_w)

png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m2.png",width=6.5,height=9,units="in",
  "in",
  res=300,type="cairo",bg="white")
print(p_w)
dev.off()

...

```{r_model_2_uncert_CI_table,echo=FALSE}
#_95%_CI_width
width95<-pred_lc$q0.975-pred_lc$q0.025

#_Land_mask_(BNG)
gb_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp,sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid)))
ov<-sp::over(pred_grid,gb_bng)
land_idx<-!is.na(ov[,1])

```

```

Land-only vector
w<-width95[land_idx&is.finite(width95)]

Summary table (land only)
w_stats<-data.frame(
 Statistic=c("Min", "Q1", "Median", "Mean", "Q3", "Max", "P90", "P99",
 "N (land)", "NAs (land)"),
 Value=c(
 min(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.25, na.rm=TRUE),
 median(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 mean(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.75, na.rm=TRUE),
 max(w, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.90, na.rm=TRUE),
 quantile(w, 0.99, na.rm=TRUE),
 sum(land_idx&is.finite(width95)),
 sum(land_idx&!is.finite(width95))
)
)

w_stats$Value<-round(w_stats$Value, 3)

knitr::kable(w_stats, align=c("l", "r"),
 caption="Model 2 (land-cover only) 95% CI
 width (fires km-2) over land pixels")

optional: save to disk
write.csv(w_stats, "m2_ciwidth_summary.csv", row.names=FALSE)

...

```{r model_3_uncert, echo=FALSE}
# Give pred_grid a data slot + 'coordinates' column, and add
  land-cover factor
pred_grid<-SpatialPointsDataFrame(pred_grid,
  data=data.frame(
    coordinates=sp::coordinates(pred_grid))
  lc_codes<-terra::extract(LC_dom, terra::vect(pred_grid))[,2]
  pred_grid$landcover<-factor(agg_lookup[as.character(lc_codes)
  ],
  levels=levels(firms_df_lc$
    landcover))

# Keep land-only and valid land-cover cells
gb_bng<-sp::spTransform(gb_sp, sp::CRS(proj4string(pred_grid)
  ))
on_land<-!is.na(sp::over(pred_grid, gb_bng)[,1])
pg<-pred_grid[on_land&!is.na(pred_grid$landcover),]

pred_log<-predict(fit_full, pg, ~landcover+field)##
  returns mean & sd for log

...

```

```

```{r,model_3_uncert_map,echo=FALSE}
coords<-sp::coordinates(pg)
sd_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1],y=coords[,2],sd=pred_log$sd)

r_sd<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(sd_xyz);raster::crs(r_sd)<-raster::crs(pg)
r_df_sd<-as.data.frame(r_sd,xy=TRUE);names(r_df_sd)<-c("x","y","sd")
r_df_sd<-r_df_sd[is.finite(r_df_sd$sd),]

gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)
p_sd<-ggplot()+
 geom_raster(data=r_df_sd,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=sd),interpolate=TRUE)+
 geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=0.4)+
 scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),name="sd(log \u03BB)",
 breaks=pretty(range(r_df_sd$sd),n=5))
)+
 coord_sf(crs=sf::st_crs(27700),default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),
 datum=sf::st_crs(4326),xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE)+
 labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+theme_bw(base_size=11)

print(p_sd)
png("lgcp_sdlog_map_m3.png",width=6.5,height=9,units="in",
 res=300,type="cairo",bg="white")
print(p_sd);dev.off()

...

```{r,model_3_uncert_table,echo=FALSE}
#Predict log-intensity( ) on land-only grid
pred_log<-predict(fit_full,pg,~landcover+field)

#sd(log ) summary over land pixels
sd_vals<-pred_log$sd

sd_stats_full<-data.frame(
  Statistic=c("Min","Q1","Median","Mean","Q3","Max","P90","P99",
  "N (land)"),
  Value=c(
    min(sd_vals,na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals,0.25,na.rm=TRUE),
    median(sd_vals,na.rm=TRUE),
    mean(sd_vals,na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals,0.75,na.rm=TRUE),
    max(sd_vals,na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals,0.90,na.rm=TRUE),
    quantile(sd_vals,0.99,na.rm=TRUE),
    sum(is.finite(sd_vals))
  )
)

```

```

)

sd_stats_full$Value<-round(sd_stats_full$Value,3)

knitr::kable(sd_stats_full,
             align=c("l","r"),
             caption="Model 3 (full)      sd(log ) over land
             pixels")

#(Optional:save)
write.csv(sd_stats_full,"m3_sdlog_summary.csv",row.names=FALSE)

#Hyperparameters
knitr::kable(fit_full$summary.hyperpar,digits=3,
             caption="Model 3 (full)      Hyperparameters")

...

```{r,model_3_uncert_CI_MAP,echo=FALSE}
#1)From existing log-scale predictions
#(if needed:pred_log<-predict(fit_full,pg,~landcover+
 field))
mu<-pred_log$mean
sigma<-pmax(pred_log$sd,0)

q025<-exp(mu+qnorm(0.025)*sigma)
q975<-exp(mu+qnorm(0.975)*sigma)
width95<-q975-q025

#2)Raster->df->ggplot
coords<-sp::coordinates(pg)
w_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1],y=coords[,2],width95=width95)
r_w<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz);raster::crs(r_w)<-raster::crs(pg)

r_df_w<-as.data.frame(r_w,xy=TRUE)
names(r_df_w)<-c("x","y","width95")
r_df_w<-r_df_w[is.finite(r_df_w$width95),]

gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)

p_w<-ggplot()+
 geom_raster(data=r_df_w,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=width95),
 interpolate=TRUE)+
 geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=0.4)+
 scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),
 name="95% CI width",
 breaks=pretty(range(r_df_w$width95),n=5))+
 coord_sf(crs=sf::st_crs(27700),default_crs=sf::st_crs(27700),

```

```

#####datum=usf::st_crs(4326),xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(
 c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE)+
labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
theme_bw(base_size=11)

print(p_w)
png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m3.png",width=6.5,height=9,units="
 in",
#####res=300,type="cairo",bg="white")
print(p_w);dev.off()

...
```{rmodel_3_uncert_CI_map_capped,echo=FALSE}
#95%CIwidthonintensityscale
mu<-pred_log$mean
sigma<-pmax(pred_log$sd,0)
q025<-exp(mu+qnorm(0.025)*sigma)
q975<-exp(mu+qnorm(0.975)*sigma)
width95<-q975-q025

#90thpercentilethreshold(land-onlygrid'pg')
thr90<-quantile(width95,0.90,na.rm=TRUE)
share_clipped<-mean(width95>thr90,na.rm=TRUE)##for
  caption/log

#Clampforplotting
coords<-sp::coordinates(pg)
w_xyz<-data.frame(x=coords[,1],y=coords[,2],
#####width95_p=upmin(width95,thr90))

#Raster->df->ggplot
r_w<-raster::rasterFromXYZ(w_xyz);raster::crs(r_w)<-
  raster::crs(pg)
r_df<-as.data.frame(r_w,xy=TRUE)
names(r_df)<-c("x","y","width95_p")
r_df<-r_df[is.finite(r_df$width95_p),]

gb_sf<-sf::st_as_sf(gb_sp)
p_w<-ggplot()+
#####geom_raster(data=r_df,aes(x=x,y=y,fill=width95_p),
  interpolate=TRUE)+
#####geom_sf(data=gb_sf,fill=NA,color="black",linewidth=
  0.4)+
#####scale_fill_gradientn(colours=rev(heat.colors(100)),
  name="95% CI width (P90 clip)",
#####breaks=pretty(range(r_df$width95_p),n=
  5))+
#####coord_sf(crs=sf::st_crs(27700),default_crs=sf::st_crs
  (27700),
#####datum=usf::st_crs(4326),xlim=c(0,700000),ylim=c(
  c(0,1300000),expand=FALSE)+
labs(x="Easting",y="Northing")+
theme_bw(base_size=11)

print(p_w)
png("lgcp_ciwidth_map_m3_p90.png",width=6.5,height=9,
  units="in",

```


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